

BLUEPRINT GUIDE

How to Create
**an Ocean of Opportunities
in the Blue Economy**

#Blue_Generation_project

The Blue Generation project is funded by Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway through the EEA and Norway Grants for Youth Employment

bluegeneration.org

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Welcome Chapter

Dear BlueGeneration friends,

It is a pleasure to welcome you to the BluePrint Guide.

We hope that you will reap of the benefits that come with reading this Guide and that you will be able to use it both as a forum for the exchange of innovative ideas and as a resource for current developments in your organization.

The main idea of the BluePrint Guide is to provide concise information about the implementation of the BlueGeneration project through the experience gained in the project countries, by presenting challenges and solutions as well as best practices and advice on how other organizations can set up the BlueGeneration Program across Europe.

It is aimed at other organizations that work with NEETs or other disadvantaged youth to transfer the BlueGeneration Program into their own context. The guide also contains general information for transferability of the BlueGeneration Program, which would help others to connect the youth sector to other economic growth sectors, e.g. the digital sector.

If you are interested in joining our BlueGeneration Federation, you may find further information in General Chapter 7 of this Guide.

Sincerely,

The BlueGeneration team

The lack of sustainable quality jobs for youth, social exclusion and discrimination are among the threats we are facing in Europe.

In this challenging context, the BlueGeneration project works to empower youth to reach their full potential. An endeavour not only crucial for the individual youth itself, but for our entire societies.

Nora Mehsen

Sector Officer and
Programme Financial
Mechanism Office –
EEA Norway Grands

General Chapter 1 **Intro**

The European Blue Economy, currently representing around 5.4 million jobs, is set to double its employment by 2030. The main challenge is, that young people are not attracted to maritime careers and therefore businesses cannot find the workforce with the required skills and competences.

At the same time, the EU has up to 10 million young people who are NEETs between 15 and 29 years and millions more who are at risk of becoming NEETs through early school dropout, difficulties in entering the labour market or personal problems.

The objective of the BlueGeneration Project is to inspire and engage these youth between 15 and 29 years to pursue a sustainable career in one of the Blue Economy growth areas: coastal tourism, aquaculture, ocean energy, marine biotechnology, ship building & maintenance, fisheries and maritime transport.

The BlueGeneration Project brings together experts from the Blue Economy and youth organizations to share knowledge about skills needs, career paths, open job positions and existing training. It also connects the above stakeholders with the Blue Economy industry, in order to familiarize youth with the reality of the blue professions and also support them to pursue training relevant with the market needs.

The BlueGeneration Project has developed the BlueGeneration Program that

- trains youth workers to become knowledgeable promoters and mentors,
- promotes Blue Career opportunities among youth through promotional activities in high schools, adult education centres, NGOs, unemployment services and local associations,

- guides interested youth through skills validation, personal mentoring and short exchanges to suitable employment and training in the Blue Economy.
- produced digital and physical tools: a MOOC, a Blue Career Guide and a Blue Career Job Platform,
- fills training gaps with short-term training opportunities that are tailored to the target group's needs,
- supports its activities with virtual reality videos of the subsectors, webinars and career pathways.

The BlueGeneration Project runs over 5 1/2 years (from June 2018 to January 2024) and will repeat the BlueGeneration Program in regular cycles to

constantly improve and firmly establish it in all partner countries.

To facilitate the transferability of the Program to other organizations, countries or contexts, the project developed this BluePrint Guide and organizes two International Conferences to inform and attract interested stakeholders.

Towards the end of 2022 the project partners are setting up a Federation that will take over ownership of all project outputs and ensure the continuation, expansion, and lasting effect of the projects' achievements.

The BlueGeneration Project is funded by the EEA and Norway Grants Fund for Youth Employment and is implemented in Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Spain with the support of Experts from Belgium, Germany, Iceland and Norway.

It is envisaged to reach up to 39,000 young people with the promotional activities and convert at least 3,300 to employment or training in the Blue Economy.

In the following sections, General Chapters about the Outputs of the project and Country reports from Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, Portugal, Rumania, and Spain will be presented.

The Country reports provide succinct information for each country regarding employment facts and trends, major advantages and resources that each country possesses in the Blue Economy. The country analysis summarizes information on training opportunities, sectors, public administration, placement agencies and promotional visits implemented in the project countries.

General Chapter 2

The BlueGeneration Program

At the heart of the project is the BlueGeneration Program. Its method is based on a Funnel Strategy (attract, engage, and convert), widely used in the marketing sector, however it is an innovative approach in the youth sector. It is supported by the transfer of good practices to include mentoring programs, skills validation tools and mobility exchanges.

The activities that have been implemented are:

1. Promotional activities

a. Organizing promotional activities (presentations, discussions face to face and on-line during the pandemic) supported by a Blue Career Guide, created specifically in the frame of the BlueGeneration Project. These activities **increase awareness** of the opportunities in the Blue Economy among NEETs providing data, facts and sharing experiences of professionals.

b. Visiting high schools, universities and university graduates associations, vocational training organizations, adult education centres, NGOs, unemployment services and local associations in order to **attract professional and educational interest** of youth.

c. The above activities are supported by the Communication strategy, publishing in all BlueGeneration Project social media photos and outcomes of the promotional activities.

2. Engagement activities

a. The BlueGeneration Project team **engage** interested youth through the Blue Careers Guide, skills validation, and personal mentoring to suitable opportunities. The mentoring sessions are the next

step after the promotional visits. Interested youth get free **mentoring sessions** with the Mentors of the BlueGeneration project also connecting them with the BlueGeneration expert's network in order to provide personalized information.

Following to the mentoring, we present the **Skills validation process** based on the skills validation toolkit. The purpose of the skills validation toolkit is to help BlueGeneration Project mentors and promoters in providing valid and up-to-date information to young trainees regarding knowledge and skills (and eventually) competences validation per beneficiary country and at EU level, according to national and EU level regulations and validation models. The **Skills validation toolkit** has placed special focus on non-formal and informal skills validation models, beyond formal ones.

Gathering **Frequently Asked Questions** by the youth who participated in the promotional visits, we created an FAQ section on the BlueGeneration project website, to allow dissemination of relevant information to the interested visitor.

b. Increase the **transnational engagement and inspiration** of youth through short international study visits and virtual study visits using 3D video, aiming to convey the reality of Blue Economy sectors on -site to an even larger number of youth, during the Covid19 pandemic and beyond.

FAQ #3

MARINE BIOTECHNOLOGY

Which are the innovative products and services that marine biotechnology offers?

ANSWER

Marine biotechnology is a rich source of materials and resources that are being used in pharmaceutical products, nutritional supplements, cosmetics, biofuels and fertilizers, food and medication for aquaculture. EU promotes the development of marine biotechnology through the making of innovative biodegradable products and the production of goods based on sea weed and algae.

Dr. Thaleia Arvaniti
Program Manager SUBMARINER,
Network for Blue Growth EEIG

www.bluegeneration.org

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3. Convert to employment and/or training

This is where we successfully bring young people into the Blue Economy.

- Support NEETs in the use of the **Blue Career Job Platform** to find employment and training.
- Liaise with the Blue Economy industry**, and specifically HR managers, signing MoU with Professional Associations, presenting to them the Blue Careers Job Platform and the benefits of the BlueGeneration Project and encourage them to publish job ads on the platform.
- The BlueGeneration team also enriches the content of the BlueCareers Job Platform with the **educational / vocational training** opportunities that exist in all partner countries.
- Provide free **short training courses** that lead to employment in one of the sectors of the Blue Economy.

The BlueGeneration Program is repeated in 4 1/2 cycles, each lasting from January to October, and followed by an evaluation and improvement process. In the first year the Blue Career Job Platform and Blue Career Guide was developed and then constantly updated by the expert partners and their industry networks.

General Chapter 3 Blue Career Guide

The Blue Career Guide constitutes the Outcome of an innovative approach to reduce youth unemployment, by combining the Blue Economy and Youth Work.

It is the first step of the project to connect the Youth Sector and the Blue Economy. For this, the Blue Economy expert partners gathered relevant information about job and training opportunities in their sub-sectors and shared this information with the youth sector workers in a 2-day exchange seminar, with the result of creating a printed version and an online version of the Blue Career Guide.

The Blue Career Guide is the main promotional tool that aims to attract, inform and guide NEETs, youth at risk of becoming NEETs and in general youth between 15 – 19 years old, about the working areas of the Blue Economy: coastal tourism, aquaculture, ocean energy, marine biotechnology, shipbuilding and maintenance, maritime transport and fisheries.

It is available in both printed form for distribution to NEETs during the promotion activities and on all meetings and events: conferences, shows, seminars, etc. and as an online version. The printed version has been updated once, whereas the online version is regularly reviewed and updated annually by the expert partners with market data, videos, links, interviews etc.

In order to explain the need of this project, the information below illustrates the situation of youth unemployment in Europe and, more specifically, in the countries that are engaged in the BlueGeneration project.

1) Situation of youth, NEETs and employment in beneficiary partners countries

The number of young people neither in employment, education or training rose during the 2008's financial and economic crisis. Almost one in ten jobs held by young people were lost since the beginning of the crisis, with the most catastrophic job losses in Spain and Greece, which saw youth employment cut in half, whilst in Portugal, about one-third of all jobs held by young people were destroyed (OECD 'Society in a Glance 2016').

In April 2022, 2.6 million young persons (under 25) were unemployed in the EU and actively looking for a job. In April 2022, the youth unemployment rate was 13.9 % in the EU, down from 14.0 % in the previous month. Compared with April 2021, youth unemployment increased by 685 000 in the EU

(Eurostat April 2022). During the pandemic in 2020, the youth unemployment rate went up to 19% in the EU and almost 20% in the Euro area.

In all partner countries, youth unemployment rates (under 25s) and NEET 15-29 years old rates are very high:

■ **Greece** has the highest rate of young unemployed persons under 25, with over 32%.

In 2021, in Greece 17% of all young people aged 15–29 were neither in employment, education or training. In 2021, the NEET rate for people aged 15–29 with a low level of education (pre-primary, primary and lower secondary education) was 8%, whilst for those with an intermediate level of education the NEET rate was higher than 18%. Concerning people aged 15-29 with a high level of education, their NEET rate was of 26%. (Eurostat, 'Statistics on young people neither in employment nor in education or training', 2021)

- **Spain**, in 2021, had 14.1% of NEETs under 30 and in April 2022, 222,000 young people under 25 were registered as unemployed.
- **Portugal**, in April 2022, had 20 % of young people under 25 that were unemployed and 10 % of all youth under 30 were neither in employment nor in education or training.
- In **Poland**, NEET rates for people aged 15–29 with a low level of education are 2 times higher than those with a high level of education. In 2021, a total of 14% of young people under 30 were NEETs.
- In **Bulgaria**, as in 2021, the NEET rate of young people (15–29) with a low level of education is 25%, among the highest in the EU (Eurostat, 2021), and has the biggest rates differences between cities and rural areas with almost 20 points.
- In **Romania**, as in 2021, 20% of all youth under 30 years were NEETs. It had a big variation between the number of NEETs with low education (33%) and high education (10%). Gender differences in the NEET rates are important, with women that are NEETs doubling the number of men NEETs for the same age group. NEET rates are also much higher in rural areas (27%) than in cities (9%).

2) Blue Economy and youth: BlueGeneration Project

The European Blue Economy, currently representing around 5.4 million jobs, is set to double its employment by 2030. The problem is that young people are not being attracted to maritime careers and businesses cannot find the required workforce, skills and profiles (European Commission SWD (2017) 130).

At the same time, 13.1% of the population aged 15–29 are NEETs (Eurostat, 2021) and millions more are at risk of becoming NEETs through early school drop-out, difficulties in entering the labor market or personal problems.

The BlueGeneration Project intends to build ways of making the match between the different sectors of the blue economy and youth, by promoting career opportunities in the Blue Economy to these young people.

The Blue Career Guide is one of the main tools to accomplish this objective. This Guide is offered to all youth that participate in promotional visits. It is a way of promoting discussion about the sectors, to rise curiosity amongst the audience and to provide a first basic set of information. The feedback after promotional visits is very positive, being considered informative, with an attractive design and making youth rethink their career options.

The Blue Career Guide is used in all dissemination activities of the project. A particularly successful dissemination activity is the participation in the European Maritime Day (EMD). The EMD is the annual EU meeting point on maritime affairs and blue growth. It targets maritime professionals, entrepreneurs and ocean leaders from businesses, governments, public institutions, NGOs and academia and is a great opportunity to present BlueGeneration Project and engage more people on it.

At the EMD in 2019 in Portugal, representatives from Militos Consulting S.A., Sea Teach, Clube Intercultural Europeu, Contextos, European Boating Industry and Submariner Network facilitated a workshop “Youth in Blue Economy”, that brought together beneficiary and expert partners introducing the project and discussing the importance of the Blue Economy sectors for youth and their future careers. At the end of the workshop, every attendant received a Blue Career Guide.

At the EMD 2022 the BlueGeneration Project was awarded the 1st prize of the “EU4Ocean in Action” Awards for its significant achievements in bringing the Blue Economy to young people and mobilizing them to pursue a relevant career.

3) Exchanging Blue Economy expertise and knowledge

The development of the Blue Career Guide, for the first time, brings together the representatives of the two sectors: the Blue Economy and Youth Work. The partnership closely collaborated to develop the materials promoting employment and training opportunities in the Blue Economy to attract the projects' target groups to a career in the Blue Economy.

In the first activities, the expert partners researched and gathered materials about the job market, training and education in their respective Blue Economy sub-sectors. The whole process of the collection of the material was coordinated by the lead partner Militos and supported by Sea Teach.

In a joint 2-day Expert Seminar the experts then informed the partners engaged in youth work about the skills needs, job opportunities and trainings available in their sectors and jointly discussed suitable pathways and presentation options for the NEETs target groups.

After the seminar, the experts formulated and structured the information of their subsectors, which then was gathered by Sea Teach to assemble

the Blue Career Guide. The Guide is available in two versions: a print version of about 30 pages and an online version.

The Blue Career Guide print version presents the seven sub-sectors as well as the job opportunities, along with the employment status at national level or EU level. It also includes a special interview with a Blue Economy professional per sector at the end of each chapter, in order to attract NEETs to the idea and opportunities of a career in the Blue Economy, but not overload them with too much information. The Lead partner, Militos Consulting SA prepared the guide for publication by designing the layout with the aim of being informative and appealing to NEETs.

The online version is more extensive, including more detailed information, videos of role models and success stories and many online links for further information.

As a result of these activities the completed Blue Career Guide is available in the six beneficiary partner languages plus English and constitutes the Outcome of an innovative approach to lower youth unemployment, by combining the Blue Economy and Youth Work.

General Chapter 4

Blue Careers Job Platform

Introduction

One of the main tools to engage young people to pursue a sustainable career in the Blue Economy, is the Blue Careers Job Platform which is available at www.bluegeneration.careers.

The Blue Careers Job Platform is the free Job Platform of the BlueGeneration Project that connects young people between 15 to 29 years with institutions and employers in the Blue Economy growth areas, specifically the sub-sectors of coastal tourism, shipbuilding and maintenance, ocean energy, marine biotechnology, fisheries, maritime transport and aquaculture.

The European Blue Economy currently represents millions of jobs and is set to increase its employment in the coming years. Therefore, many maritime businesses and training centres are

looking to attract young people into exciting Blue Economy careers.

BlueGeneration has generated a unique Blue Economy network that connects employers, training institutions and job seekers in Europe.

Structure and functionality

The General Structure of the platform consists of a) a landing page, where the user can search for a job, training or internship with a search bar. This offers the possibility to filter the type of offer by one of the seven main sub-sectors the project promotes, by location, by language and by keywords. On the same landing page, a graphical search-wheel offers specific sub-sector selection by icons,

- b) a targeted navigation to the pages for finding a job, training or internship, filtering the specific offers by category,
- c) an option for registered users to post their offers in the categories of job, training or internship,
- d) information about the project-funding EEA and Norway Grants Fund for Youth Employment,
- e) information about the BlueGeneration Project with link to its main website,
- f) a contact form, with the possibility to download the Blue Career Guide,
- g) account options, for registered users to edit their job seeker profile or their employers' profile.
- h) language options, with multiple European languages to select.

The Blue Career Job Platform offers two different registration and log-in options for

- Job seekers
- Employers and Training organisations

JOB SEEKERS

Young people who have been attracted into the Blue Economy and are engaged in finding new working or training opportunities can:

- search for a job, training or internship,
- register & log-in for notifications of available services,
- upload their CVs and share their profile,
- apply for a job, training or courses, and
- contact the BlueGeneration team.

The 'job seeker' can upload a CV with the application, add some comments, add a cover letter and share the personal profile. Job seekers have the option to register with a basic profile with general information such as name, contact details, description, country, and age.

Additionally, the platform offers Job seekers the option to provide a much more detailed profile, the 'shared profile' which includes curricular information such as experience, education and courses or skills. When applying for a job offer, job seekers can opt for or against sharing this detailed information with the employer of training organisation.

EMPLOYERS AND TRAINING ORGANISATIONS

For posting jobs, internships or trainings, a few basic information fields can be completed with the information about the offer, these include title, country, sub-sector, contract type, language, contact details, description of the offer, requirements, salary, start date, study mode, location, and fee (if applicable). After providing this information, registered 'job seekers' will be able to apply for the offer through the webpage, in which case the 'employer' will receive a notification in his platform account and per email.

Employers and organizations who want to promote their job opportunities, training possibilities or internships can:

- post a job,
- post a training,
- post an internship,
- modify the company details,
- visualize the shared profiles of people who applied on their offers,
- see and modify their offers, and
- receive applications, including the applicant's personal details as far as they are provided by the applicant.

Promotion

The promotion of the job platform is done through the direct contact with job providers at regional level, offering local providers the possibility to post offers free of charge.

At national level, job, training or internship offers are provided by contacting the umbrella associations that represent the different subsectors of the Blue Economy, i.e. aquaculture, coastal tourism, ocean energy, marine biotechnology, shipbuilding and repair, maritime transport or fisheries.

At international level, job, training or internship offers can be provided by contacting major trade and business associations that represent the different Blue Economy sectors in Europe.

This cooperation helps to maintain an active network of Blue Economy companies and institutions throughout Europe, promoting blue careers for young people.

The Blue Career Job Platform is available in multiple European languages.

General Chapter 5 **BlueGeneration MOOC**

The BlueGeneration MOOC, is a Massive Open Online Course that is freely available for the interested user.

It aims at youth workers and intermediaries who want to learn more background information about the Blue Economy in Europe, and then deliver this information to interested youth through promotional visits and mentoring and become a mentor for the BlueGeneration project. It can certainly also be used directly by youth to acquire a 360 view of the Blue Economy employment professions and employment conditions.

The **BlueGeneration MOOC delivers knowledge about different marine-based economical activities in Europe**, explaining the potential growth and jobs for different sectors. It also explains, what job opportunities exist for young people in the different sub-sectors and what training opportunities and further education can be done. The MOOC requires a total approximate learning duration of about 20 hours which are spread over 10 modules.

The training starts with **two introductory modules** which include a general introduction chapter about the courses' aims and structure and an explanation

about the Blue Economy in Europe. Each of the two first modules consists of a video, a section with general information about the Blue economy, links, infographics, and additional videos. Finally, they have a quiz with 6 questions to test the acquired knowledge.

The **following 7 modules** explain in detail the seven subsectors of the Blue Economy: as coastal tourism, aquaculture, ocean energy, marine biotechnology, shipbuilding, maritime transport, and fisheries. Every module includes an introductory video from an expert in the specific sub-sector, explaining some general details about this part of the industry in Europe. This is followed by a short quiz of three questions to test the acquired knowledge.

In a next step, a longer video of about 10 minutes explains in detail the most important information about each of the sub- sectors in Europe. They particularly explain the indicators and opportunities of the job market, the overall status in terms of growth and numbers of jobs, and information about available training. This knowledge will be tested by another short quiz of three questions.

Finally, every sector-specific module contains a section with further information, including links, infographics and videos for further studying. At the end of each module a final quiz tests the knowledge acquired about the sub-sector. It requires a passing grade of 70% to complete the module and unlock the next module.

Module number 9 contains a video about general presentation skills and how to present the BlueGeneration project in promotional visits and mentoring for young people.

The last module, number 10, consists of a general quiz about the entire course content and after passing it with at least 70%, the mentor/ student can unlock access to materials for promoting the BlueGeneration Project. This includes templates for presentations, promotional materials, the BlueCareer Guide, for printing and online, further information about the sectors and job opportunities, the Blueprint Guide with information on how to implement the BlueGeneration Project in different contexts.

After completing the course, the participants have enough knowledge to be able to promote Blue Economy jobs to young people and guide them to find adequate training and careers paths, thus becoming enabled to work as a mentor for the BlueGeneration Project.

All videos are edited professionally and are in English with subtitles of different European languages. They contain information that can be used not only for persons interested in becoming a mentor for the BlueGeneration project, but also by all the interested persons who want to learn more about the Blue Economy, its sectors, career perspectives, job opportunities, available trainings and further education paths.

The BlueGeneration MOOC is a great opportunity for anyone to learn more about the Blue Economy, and especially for those who wish to become a mentor. Also interested youth can learn more background information about the Blue Economy and its sub-sectors in Europe.

The screenshot shows the BlueGeneration MOOC Platform interface. On the left, a sidebar lists the course progress: 3% complete. The course is divided into modules, with the following details visible:

Module	Progress
Survey	1/1
Module 0. Welcome to the course!	1/1
What is the course about and how is it built	TEXT - FREE PREVIEW
Module 1. Intro and Blue economy	0/3
Module 2. Coastal Tourism	0/6
Module 3. Aquaculture	0/6
Module 4. Ocean energy	0/6
Module 5. Marine Biotechnology	0/6
Module 6. Shipbuilding and maintenance	0/6
Module 7. Maritime Transport	0/6

The main content area displays 'MODULE 0 Welcome to the course' with a video player. Below the video, there are links for 'Download video' and 'Download transcription'. The text below the video reads: 'This course is intended for training mentors to do promotional visits and mentoring in the scope of the Blue Generation Project. After finishing this course you will be able to promote blue economy jobs to young people and assess them to find adequate training or careers paths. Also, you will be provided with tips and a toolkit for promotional visits. The general structure and timeframe for learning per module will be as follows:'

- **Module 1.** Introduction about the Blue economy - 1 hour
- **Module 2.** Coastal Tourism - 2 hours
- **Module 3.** Aquaculture - 2 hours
- **Module 4.** Ocean energy - 2 hours

At the bottom of the page, there are buttons for 'MARK INCOMPLETE' and 'CONTINUE'.

The BlueGeneration MOOC is freely available at www.bluegenerationmoooc.thinkific.com

General Chapter 6 Communication

Introduction

Communication is the key element in the BlueGeneration Project and includes internal and external communication. A Communication Plan defines the external communication strategy which aims at different target groups and stakeholders.

The internal communication defines the communication amongst the partners (a) monthly partner meetings (physical and virtual) both with beneficiary but also with expert partners after which respective Minutes of Meeting are circulated, (b) 1-2-1 meetings with the Coordinator, Militos, supporting partners in planning & reporting (c) emails, calls, messages between the Coordinator and all partners to follow-up of project activities, to coordinate deliverables, to clarify issues, to exchange best practices. Also close communication is needed with the Fund Operator to receive guidance, to share achievements and risks. The Project Management Platform "AdminProject" is the main tool for internal communication.

Why is the communication plan so important for the BlueGeneration?

Communication is a key element because the success of the BlueGeneration project greatly relies on the successful planning and implementation of the communication strategy and its related activities. The implementation of the BlueGeneration Program, Blue Career Guide, Blue Career Job Platform, BluePrint Guide and Federation required to build up and maintain a new network that (a) supports the content and relevant updates, (b) contributes with their knowledge and experience in creating digital tools relevant to youth, especially the BlueGeneration's target group of NEETs, (c) connects the project with Youth Organizations, Employment agencies and (d) offers insights on training and skills requirements of the Blue Economy job market. The BlueGeneration communication approach is based on a solid communication strategy disseminated and implemented consistently by all partners in all partner countries, considering local needs, legal frames, and cultural characteristics.

The poster features a blue header with logos for Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway grants. The main title is "BlueGeneration" in white on a blue background, followed by "Promoting Blue Economy" in white on a yellow background. Below this is the text "JOBS FOR YOUNG PEOPLE IN EUROPE" in blue. The central part of the poster shows a hand holding a white card with a list of blue economy sectors: COASTAL TOURISM, aquaculture, ocean energy, marine biotechnology, shipbuilding, MARITIME TRANSPORT, and fisheries. At the bottom, the website "www.bluegeneration.org" is displayed, along with a note about funding from Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway through the EEA Grants and Norway Grants Fund for Youth Employment. The footer lists the implementing partners: militos, SEA TEACH, abs, FRSP, CLUBE INTERCULTURAL EUROPEU, SEA Europe, EBI, HEBUMPA, and TEAM 4.

Moreover, the innovative approach of the BlueGeneration Project, which is to bring together two different sectors - blue economy and youth-whose needs complement each other is at a wide extent a communication challenge. This communication challenge requires clear messages to specific targets with a high level of interaction between the sectors and careful selection of the communication media utilized to achieve the main goal of the project: to disseminate employment and training opportunities that are available in the Blue Economy to young people and NEETs and to make stakeholders and employers in the Blue Economy aware of the unexploited potential of NEETs that can be recruited as the much-needed young workforce.

The communication strategy follows two types of objectives, 1) transversal and 2) specific. The transversal objectives are those which are present in all stages of the project whereas the specific ones are linked to particular activities or work packages.

In general, the targeted audience of the BlueGeneration Project are all stakeholders directly or indirectly involved who will benefit from the projects' outputs/outcomes or stakeholders whose contribution could benefit the project outputs/outcomes.

To ensure the efficiency of the communication plan, below we describe the specific target audiences that the BlueGeneration Project aims for, which information each targeted audience receives, what is the purpose of each type of communication and which means and media should be selected.

1 BLUEGENERATION WEBSITE

In all partner languages (English, Spanish, Portuguese, Polish, Bulgarian and Romanian). This website contains all the information related to the project, its outcomes and outputs. The main goal of the website is to integrate all digital tools in a user friendly way, making it attractive to the youth and present to them all information in order to support them in their career journey to the Blue Economy. There is a special section where all news, press releases, events are published, and that is renewed regularly in order to provide always interesting content to the visitor. As it is designed to attract the public, the language used is simple, succinct, non-technical and easy to read. It is ensured that the contribution of the EEA and Norway Grants Fund for Youth employment is presented in a clear and visible way. The coordinator, Militos, developed the website and in cooperation with SeaTeach upgraded the content

and functionality to be combined with the Job Platform to form an Integrated BlueGeneration Platform. This website can evolve and become the BlueGeneration Federation website after the BlueGeneration Project has been concluded. It is regularly updated and enriched in order to remain attractive and relevant to its audience.

2 BLUEGENERATION PARTNER WEBSITES

Each partner has set up information about their collaboration with the BlueGeneration Project on their own website and has made the contribution of the EEA and Norway Grants Fund for Youth employment visible. The partner websites update the information regularly and include a direct link into the project website. All stakeholders who will be involved in the BlueGeneration Federation after BlueGeneration Project completion will be required to do the same.

3 BLUEGENERATION PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Flyers, roll-ups, posters, banners, pens, t-shirts, hats and bags are important to spread the message of the project during the major events and also attract

youth. The promotional material is either physical or digital and is designed by a professional graphic designer. The coordinator, Militos, oversees that those materials are in line with the BlueGeneration Brand and that it displays the contribution of the EEA and Norway Grants Fund for Youth employment. All Partners logos are presented along where feasible. Below indicative printed flyers and banners, some of them specifically designed for specific uses, e.g. to promote digital tools and attract youth in the Blue Careers Platform, raise awareness, invite in various events and create a powerful brand.

4 MAJOR EVENTS

A total of nine major events had been planned to increase the dissemination of the project outputs and activities. In the timeline these were planned to alternate between large international events such as conferences or boat-shows and national events in form of seminars held in each beneficiary partner country. Whilst the international events predominantly aimed at high-level stakeholders from the Blue Economy, Youth Sector and international organisations, the national events are more directed towards the national youth-work sector and national and local stakeholders. The unfortunate event of the Covid19 pandemic, was a challenge in the implementation of many of the planned events. However the versatility

General Chapter 7

BlueGeneration Federation

The BlueGeneration project is designed to carry out its activities also after the end of the initial funding by the EEA and Norway Grants.

The purpose of the BlueGeneration Federation is to continue bringing together stakeholders from the Youth Sector and stakeholders from the Blue Economy Sector with the aim to inspire and engage young people and especially NEETs to pursue sustainable careers in the Blue Economy.

The BlueGeneration Federation is initially transforming the partner collaboration of the BlueGeneration Project consortium into a membership-based federation. At the same time, it is also open for other stakeholders to join.

Applicants are accepted as members by the governing board of the BlueGeneration Federation in line with the statutes of the Federation.

In particular the following stakeholders are invited to join as members:

- Organisations working in or with the Youth Sector in Europe or any Mediterranean neighbour countries.
- Organisations working in or with the Blue Economy Sector in Europe or any Mediterranean neighbour countries.

These stakeholders can be local, national or European non-profit associations, SMEs, umbrella organisations, professional associations, research centres, training providers or public bodies.

The aim of the BlueGeneration Federation is to build a wide and strong coalition of members that can effectively continue the work of the BlueGeneration Project and expand its implementation and impact.

The BlueGeneration Federation has ownership of all outputs produced by the BlueGeneration Project, which include:

- The BlueGeneration Website
- The BlueGeneration social media pages in Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter and Instagram, TikTok
- The BlueGeneration multilingual promotional materials including flyers, press kits, roll-ups, posters and promotional videos
- The Blue Career Guide in printed and online versions
- The Blue Career Job Platform at www.bluegeneration.careers
- The BlueGeneration MOOC at www.bluegenerationmooc.thinkific.com
- The BlueGeneration Program with all its presentation documents and tips, PowerPoint templates, validation tool lists, mentoring packages, stakeholder contacts and evaluation and control mechanisms.
- The BlueGeneration training courses

Members will benefit from their participation in the BlueGeneration Federation in multiple ways:

- a** Create awareness as employers thus building upon their employer's brand and attracting young professionals focused at the Blue Economy,
- b** Gain publicity to the consumers and businesses and having the opportunity to improve their ESG profile
- c** Increase opportunities to partner with relevant entities in EU projects and have access to respective funding
- d** Utilize all BlueGeneration assets, i.e physical and digital tools and materials, free use of the Blue Careers Job Platform
- e** Get support by a professional and experienced back-up office that is available for advice and support and have priority to attend large international networking events.

Maritime clusters, Blue Economy associations, Donors, the EEA and Norway Grants program, the EU Commission and other stakeholders are invited to support the work of the BlueGeneration Federation through funding and networking mechanisms.

Country Report **Bulgaria**

I. TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES

In Bulgaria there exist several opportunities for gaining an academic proficiency or a professional training related to the different sub-sectors, within the Blue Economy.

In general school education in Bulgaria starts at the age of seven.

a. High school education

High school education is conducted in 'General education' schools (3 and 4 years of study) and in specialized schools (4 and 5 years of study). Students are admitted to specialized or vocational schools after passing entrance exams after 6th or 7th grade in Bulgarian language and literature, mathematics, humanities, etc. Restrictions based on race, nationality, sex, ethnic and social origin, religion and social status are forbidden.

Specialized subjects related to the Blue Economy sub-sectors are accessible in Professional High Schools (5 school years of education, up to 12th grade) and provide qualification for different Tourism related activities or Tourism Management,

through full- and part- time courses.

The Marine High School in Varna¹ offers specialization in Sea Navigation; Ship machines and mechanisms; Electrical equipment of the ship; Operation of ports and fleet; Forwarding, transport and warehousing logistics. The Professional High School for Sailing and Fisheries "Sveti Nikola"² in Burgas is another example that offers specializations in Sea Navigation, and Ship machines and mechanisms, as well as Maritime administration. The last high school dedicated to Maritime is the Professional High School of River Shipbuilding and Navigation³, located in Ruse, a city on the Danube river. The School offers the following courses: Ship Machines and Mechanisms; River Navigation; Electrical equipment of ships; Operation of ports and fleet; Shipbuilding; Freight and services logistics; Welding; Vacancies in PGRKK by classes.

1 www.vmg.bg

2 school.morskoburgas.com

3 www.pgrkk-ruse-bg.net

b. Higher education

With regard to higher education, it should be noted that the Law in Bulgaria provides full autonomy in the activities of higher education institutions. The system of higher education organizes training after completing secondary education for acquiring the following educational and qualification degrees:

- 1 Educational qualification degree "bachelor", for the acquisition of which in accordance with the curriculum are required:
 - not less than 180 credits with a term of study of not less than three years - "professional bachelor in";
 - not less than 240 credits with a term of study of not less than 4 years - "bachelor".
 - The education in the degree "bachelor" under par. 1, item 1 in accordance with the curriculum provides wide-profile training or specialized professional training in professional fields and specialties.
- 2 Educational qualification degree "master", for the acquisition of which are required:
 - not less than 300 credits according to the curriculum with a term of study of not less than 5 years;
 - not less than 120 credits after the acquired educational-qualification degree "professional bachelor in ...";
 - not less than 60 credits after obtaining a bachelor's degree.
 - Master's degree training provides in-depth fundamental training combined with profiling in a specific specialty.
- 3 Educational and scientific degree "Doctor":
The training is organized in doctoral programs after obtaining the educational qualification degree "Master". The term of preparation and independent research work for regular and independent form of education is up to 3 years, and for part-time and distance - up to 4 years. Exceptionally, regulated in the regulations of the respective higher school or scientific organization, the term may be extended, but by no more than one year.

Related to the Blue Economy examples of acquiring a professional degree might be through a college educational institution. Examples include

"College of Tourism Blagoevgrad"⁴; "College of Tourism Varna"⁵. The colleges however give a practical type of education and do not lead to any further type of degree, Master, etc.

University studies are a more formal type of education, where specific university subjects related to Aquaculture or Biotechnology could be studied at various public universities. Examples include "Sofia University"⁶ or medical universities "Medical University Sofia"⁷.

Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy⁸ is the only higher educational institution in Bulgaria that is entirely dedicated to sea careers and maritime education. It offers studies in Shipbuilding; Marine Transport and other ship maintenance or transport management related programs. The academy is the oldest technical educational institution in Bulgaria. It offers education to Cadets as well as Bachelor, Masters and Doctor degrees. The duration of the course to become a Cadet, for example, is 5 years. Two parallel and simultaneous major programs underlie the cadets' training: Navy Task Group Organization and Control as well as Marine Engineering. On successful graduation cadets acquire two B. Sc. Degrees in the respective majors.

- Naval Warfare Officers
- Engineers for the Navy
- Naval Communications Officers

The Academy furthermore offers short-term courses, such as "Specialized Training for Personnel on Passenger Ships"; "Proficiency in Medical First Aid"; "Proficiency in survival craft and rescue boats".

c. Private Education

In Bulgaria a candidate may not qualify for a governmentally covered higher education student status quota, because of low results on exams. However, most of the subjects at public universities can still be studied, but for a certain payment. Other than the public universities Bulgaria also has a private ones and private colleges. Examples of such institutions include The New Bulgarian

4 cotur.bg

5 www.ct-varna.com/index-0en.html

6 www.uni-sofia.bg/

7 bit.ly/3QYtKvx

8 www.naval-acad.bg/en/about-us

University⁹; The Inter Business College¹⁰, that offers specialization in hotel management, cuisine and tourism and many others. An example of a private academy for acquiring a sailing license, is Karela Sailing¹¹. The academy offers specific short-term courses with which a person can qualify as a skipper of a small charter ship.

d. VET Education

Vocational education refers to secondary education programs provided by VET schools. This type of education includes a general education element and is provided for learners from age 16. It does not include general education, which needs to be acquired prior to entering vocational training; qualifications are distinct from certificates attesting education levels (such as basic, secondary and higher); they can be acquired in addition to certificates and are linked to a profession.

The requirements for enrolment in VET programs are minimum age, health condition, previous education and qualification level. The minimum required age is 13 (in the year of application) for vocational gymnasiums and schools. It is 16 for vocational training centres (initial and continuing VET providers for employees and the unemployed, without acquisition of an education level). The health condition of the applicant is attested by a medical certificate indicating fitness for the selected occupation. Previous education requirements are at least a completed primary, basic or secondary education or a successfully completed literacy course under the employment promotion Act.

VET providers and their respective numbers according to 2016/2017 official report on Vocational Education and training in Bulgaria¹²:

- VET schools (provide education and training):
 - vocational gymnasiums (373);
 - vocational classes in general education schools;
 - art schools (22);
 - sports schools (24);
- adult training institutions (provide training only):
 - vocational colleges (36);
 - vocational training centers (1006).

⁹ nbu.bg

¹⁰ www.interbusiness-bg.net/bg/index.php

¹¹ karela-sailing.com

¹² www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/4161_en.pdf

In the list of VET specializations¹³, related to the Blue Economy there are distinguished studies e.g.: Energy sector; Industrial electrical equipment; Marine electrical equipment; Power equipment and installations fitter; Steam and water heating systems operator; Chemical products and technologies; Food and beverage Industry technologies; Hotels, restaurants and catering; Travel, tourism and leisure, etc.

An example of another specific certification that could be acquired is within the Red Cross¹⁴ organization and is for becoming an authorized lifeguard.

II. SECTORS

In Bulgaria not all of the sectors within the “BlueGeneration” project, are clearly differentiated and presented by a company or organization. However, the biggest one remains the **Coastal tourism** with relation to all the accommodation services and tourism in Coastal Regions. The hospitality sector (including hotels and catering) and the nautical tourism industry are the two most important subsectors. The coastal tourism on the Bulgarian Black Sea is an important part of the tourism industry and requires and provides many opportunities for professional development.

The **Fisheries** and **Aquaculture** sub-sectors are mainly represented by “Yara”¹⁵ - Fisheries and Aquaculture Executive Agency, which is the main organization operating under the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry. The agency manages the fishing and aquaculture activities and also recreational fishing.

The largest **Shipbuilding** company, that exists in Bulgaria and representative of the sub-sector is “Bulyard Industry”¹⁶. The shipyard in Varna is a symbol of tradition, quality and security of its products. The foundations of the enterprise were laid in 1907. To this date, more than 850 ships have been built and put into service for 27 state-owned countries and sail around the world under the flags of more than 22 countries.

¹³ bit.ly/3PX3AYM

¹⁴ www.redcross.bg

¹⁵ iara.government.bg

¹⁶ bulyard.com

Bulyard Shipbuilding Industry AD annually repairs over 60 vessels of various types:

- Cargo ships
- Tankers
- Gas trucks
- Drilling ships
- Platform maintenance ships

Some of the most prominent clients of Bulyard KI AD are Noble Corporation, Tsakos Group and many others.

The state enterprise “Port Infrastructure”¹⁷ is the leading institution for building e-governance in **Maritime transport**. It manages the port infrastructure of the public transport ports of national importance and provides traffic management and shipping information services. Object of activity and status of BPI Co. are regulated by the Law on Maritime Spaces, Inland Waterways and Ports of the Republic of Bulgaria. Its head office is located in Sofia and in Burgas, Varna, Lom and Ruse are four branches of Territorial Directorates and Specialized Divisions.

The **Marine Biotechnology** sub-sector finds application in various research institutes and centers, where research related to the biological transformation of raw materials and information (e.g. genes) derived from aquatic resources and production of organic products is carried out;

17 www.bgports.bg/en

research, control and production units of the biotechnological, chemical and pharmaceutical industries.

An example of a representative institution is the Institute of Microbiology “Stefan Angelov”¹⁸, which is a national scientific center for microbiological research. From its foundation until today, its main goals are research on health, agriculture and industry, as well as training of doctoral students and young specialists.

Another example is the National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa” in Constanta (www.rmri.ro) which is mainly involved in basic research and applied technology, crucial for the understanding, protection and management of coastal and marine environment in the economic exclusive zone of Romania at the Black Sea coast.

Its main areas of research include marine biology and microbiology, marine chemistry and biochemistry, applied ecology and aquaculture, marine pollution management of fishery resources, and engineering and marine technology.

“KEBP”/KEVR/¹⁹ is the state organization, known as Energy and Water Regulatory Commission, that is responsible for all activities regarding the **Ocean Energy** sub-sector of the Blue Economy in Bulgaria. However, in general Bulgaria does not rely on energy, produced from ocean power.

III. PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The established sectors within the Blue Economy are falling under regional and national administrative units.

The **Fisheries** sub-sector and parts of the **Aquaculture** sector fall under the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry²⁰. This is a supreme body of state power that conducts state policy in the field of agriculture, forestry, and since 1989 also in the field of water.

The **Ocean Energy** sector falls under the Ministry of Environment²¹ and Water and the Ministry of Economy, Energy and Tourism²². The Ministry of Environment and Water defines national policies, strategies, prepares standards and priorities

18 microbio.bas.bg/wordpress/index.php/za-nas/

19 www.dker.bg

20 www.mzh.government.bg/bg

21 bit.ly/3D1gIPi

22 mi.government.bg/bg

for environmental protection. The Ministry of Economy, Energy and Tourism designs, researches, and is responsible for maintenance and operation of energy facilities in the country, production and transmission of heat and electricity, extraction and processing of ore and non-ore minerals, use of water resources for electricity generation and others.

The sub-sectors **Aquacultures** and **Biotechnology** fall under the Ministry of Education and Science²³ and the Ministry of Environment and Water. The Ministry of Education and Science manages and supervises the educational, cultural and educational instances in the country.

The **Coastal Tourism** is assigned to the above-mentioned Ministry of Economy, Energy and Tourism and the Ministry of Culture²⁴. Ministry of Culture manages and coordinates the cultural sites on the territory of the country and conducts its cultural policy. Under its jurisdiction are also cultural monuments, museums, historical sites, theaters, opera, ballet, some high schools of national importance. The Ministry carries out international cooperation in the field of culture, issues licenses for protection of copyright and controls Bulgarian cultural institutes

Shipbuilding and **Marine Transport** are both assigned to Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications²⁵, which conducts government policy in the field of transport, information technology and communications.

IV. PLACEMENT AGENCIES

The main official Bulgarian "Employment Agency"²⁶ operates under the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy and leads several programs that are designed to help with the employment of disadvantaged people or youths with fewer opportunities.

The DEMO Association²⁷ is the only private Bulgarian NGO, whose main aim is to develop and implement European, national and international projects and programs in the field of education and employment.

DEMO PUBLIC BENEFIT ASSOCIATION is an organization in public benefit and provides:

- Vocational Training Center (VET DEMO-1)
- Information and Vocational Guidance Center (CIPO DEMO-2)
- Center for Social Integration, Legal Advice and Training (CSIPCO DEMO-3)

The centers specialize in the field of:

- Employment;
- Training in many professions and specialties;
- Career counseling and career guidance;
- Training in key competencies;
- Motivation for active behavior on the labor market;
- Social integration;
- Anti-discrimination and individual legal aid.

The DEMO Association has offices in eight regional cities in Bulgaria: Sofia, Blagoevgrad, Burgas, Varna, Vratsa, Plovdiv and Ruse.

"Top Skills"²⁸ is an example of an acquisition company cooperating with local and international companies in the search of the finest talents and helping jobseekers find their most suitable workplace. The Top Skills company are among the main recruiting companies supporting the "BlueGeneration" project for Bulgaria.

In Bulgaria there are also various other NGOs, that are specifically oriented to Marine life and that are operating in the Black Sea regions. "Black Sea Institute"²⁹ is an NGO, whose main aim is preserving and increasing all activities related to the Black Sea and Black Sea region.

Other examples include "Black Sea Biotechnology Association"; "Black Sea Center for Environmental Information and Education"³⁰; "The Black Sea Network of NGO's"³¹ "Friends of the Black Sea"³² and others.

23 www.minedu.government.bg

24 mc.government.bg

25 www.mtitc.government.bg/index.php

26 www.az.government.bg

27 www.demo-ngo.com/index.php/bg

28 topskills-bg.com/

29 blacksea.bg/

30 www.bseco.info/za_nas.html

31 www.bsnn.org/bg/za_nas.html

32 bit.ly/3PYKMbq

V. PROMOTIONAL VISITS

The “BlueGeneration” project is being promoted to the following target groups:

- High School Students aged 15-19 – aiming to capture those young individuals that are prior to graduation, so they can continue their professional development within the sphere of the Blue Economy.
- University and College students, aged 18-29 – aiming to capture those individuals under 30 that are pursuing a degree in the above-mentioned universities; or even if they are not pursuing a related to the Blue Economy degree, so they can still reconsider their options for further professional development, as the “BlueGeneration” also offers “non-specific” careers.
- Unemployed people under 30- Those young people that are interested in developing professionally within the Blue Economy, but that have encountered some employment disadvantages or difficulties.

To capture the stated target groups the BlueGeneration project works closely with the following institutions and centers:

- High Schools and Professional High Schools – where students, aged 15-19 are getting traditional or specific professional education like Hotel Management, Gastronomy, etc.
- Universities and Colleges – where students might be interested in a specific field related to BlueGeneration project or in mentoring and internships abroad.
- VET centers – centers that are offering specific courses and training programs.
- The Bulgarian Employment Agency and other adult career centers and employment organizations.
- NGO’s – other NGOs are a useful cooperation figure to attract more youth people with disadvantages or those interested in mentoring and professional development.

Country Report **Greece**

I. TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES

The different training opportunities that are offered in Greece, specifically related to the Blue Economy, either at VET Centers, Universities or other Employment Agencies, are briefly presented below.

a. Secondary education system overview

Education in Greece is compulsory for all children between the ages of 6-15 (9 years total) and includes Primary and Lower Secondary (junior high school, known as “Gymnasium”). However, the school life of students can start from the age of 2.5 years (pre-school education) in institutions (private and public) called nursery schools. Some nurseries also have kindergartens that run in parallel. Along with the common schools of Primary and Secondary Education, there are also special kindergartens, primary schools, junior high and high schools that are addressed to students with special educational needs.

Post-compulsory secondary education, following the year 2000 reform, includes two types of

schools: the General High School (named “Lyceum”, abbr. GEL) and the Vocational High Schools (EPAL). The duration of study is three years in the Unified Lyceums and two years (first cycle of studies) or three years (second cycle of studies) in the Vocational High Schools, while moving from one type of school to another is permitted. At the final stage of his/her studies, a student may work as an apprentice and gain valuable work experience.

There are also Music, Ecclesiastical and Sports Gymnasiums and Lyceums. The post-compulsory Secondary Education also includes the Vocational Training Institutes (named IEK), which offer formal but non-regulated education. These institutions are characterized as non-regulated, because they accept both lower-secondary school graduates and lyceum school graduates, depending on the specific specializations they offer.

High Schools (lyceums) offer a combination of General Education courses and Advanced Placement courses. Students who wish to pursue studies in Higher Education participate in the Annual Panhellenic exams in a specific number of Advanced Placement courses which fall into one of

the following categories: Humanities, Science, and Technology. This is considered to be a tough and highly competitive exam process that students go through in order to attend higher education (i.e. to aim for university degrees).

b. Higher Education studies

Based on the country's education system, public university education is divided into universities and technical universities. The admission of students to these institutions depends on their performance in the Annual Panhellenic exams, mentioned above. In addition, students above 22 years old have the choice to enter to the Hellenic Open University (EAP). Finally, in Greece there are private colleges (operating under a rather complicated system of rules and equivalences), in which students may enroll after completing their studies in Secondary Education. The Greek Constitution prohibits the operation of private colleges. However, several European and American universities operate in Greece in cooperation with Greek private colleges, offering the greatest part of their degree curricula locally. Students usually need to attend said universities abroad for short periods to obtain full degrees. Courses in public Greek universities are offered in the Greek language. There is one notable exception, the International University of Greece (in Thessaloniki) which offers all its undergraduate and postgraduate courses, across all its schools, in English.

At the highest level, the responsibility for the education and training of adults is shared between two ministries: the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs.

c. Lifelong Learning

As defined in Law 3879/2010, "Lifelong Learning (LL) concerns all forms of learning activities during a person's life, aimed at acquiring or developing knowledge, skills and abilities, which contribute to the formation of a complete personality, professional integration and development of the individual, in social cohesion, in the development of the ability to actively participate in the commons and in the social, economic and cultural development. It includes formal education, non-formal education and informal learning". The National Network for Lifelong Learning (EDDBM) consists of all LL bodies, which must cooperate both in terms of composing proposals and implementing actions and two-way communication.

The following agencies that manage and provide LL services form the National Lifelong Learning Network (EDDBM), in accordance with laws 3879/2010 and 4186/2013:

- Vocational Training Institutes (IEK);
- Private colleges;
- Lifelong Learning Centers (KDBM) - Level I & II;
- Any other public or private VET school;
- The Youth and Lifelong Learning Foundation (INEDIVIM);
- All Higher Education Institutions (public universities);
- The Hellenic Open University;
- Organizations providing general (formal and non-formal) adult education services, which may include social, religious and cultural institutions, as well as institutions for providing general adult education services, such as Second Chance Schools (SDEs) and Parents' Schools
- Employment Service Centers and other Organizations providing counselling services and/or vocational guidance services;
- Bodies that provide non-formal education to personnel of the public and the wider public sector (such as the EKDDA); or, bodies established by professional associations, public chambers, employers' associations and specific trade unions to provide non-formal education to their members
- Any organization offering non-typical learning services;
- The Center for Security Studies (KEMEA).

National Qualifications and Vocational Guidance Organization (EOPPEP)

EOPPEP is the competent organization for the certification of studies in the adult education bodies. It was established by law 4115/2013 as the successor body of the merger between the National Agency for Qualification Certification (EOPP), the Lifelong Learning Structures Certification Center (EKEPIS) and the National Center for Vocational Orientation (EKEP).

EOPPEP develops and implements an integrated national certification system for non-formal education and provides scientific support to the services of Vocational Orientation and Counseling in Greece. In addition, EOPPEP is responsible for the development of the National Qualifications

Framework and its alignment with the European Qualifications Framework.

Within the framework of its responsibilities, EOPPEP promoted and completed the development of the National Qualifications Framework, providing the basis for the classification of all the titles granted by the Greek educational system. On December 2, 2015, in the context of the 33rd Meeting of the Advisory Group on the European Qualifications Framework in Berlin, following the presentation of the Greek delegation, the correspondence of the National Qualifications Framework of Greece with the European Qualifications Framework was ratified.

A concise table depicting the National Qualifications System currently in effect, follows:

Level 1	Elementary School graduate	
Level 2	(Junior) High-school (a.k.a. Gymnasium) graduate	
Level 3	(VET credentials not any longer offered)	
Level 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General High School (a.k.a. Lyceum) graduate (named GEL) Vocational High School graduate (named EPAL) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Professional Vocational High School graduate (EPAL) Professional Vocational Institute graduate (named EPAS) 	
Level 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post-lyceum Professional graduate (post-lyceum EPAL) VET Institute graduate (named I.E.K) Higher Education Professional Diploma or Degree 	
	Level 6	Higher Education Diploma or Degree
	Level 7	Post-graduate degree qualification
Level 8	Doctoral degree qualification	

In addition to the above, any holders of higher education qualifications (and above) who attend Life Long or Continued Education vocational courses in accordance with existing professional qualification schemes (in order to receive updated training), are granted official Certificates of Completion.

d. VET Institutes related to Blue economy (named I.E.K)

Most of the specialties available in VET institutes (public or private) are applicable to employment in Blue Economy, e.g. Administration & Finance Officer, Computerized Accounting & Tax Officer, Network and Telecommunications Technician, Culinary Arts Technician – Chef, and Tourist Guide. There are also specialized courses dedicated to specific sectors of the Blue Economy, e.g. Management and Finance Executive in the Shipping Sector or Shipbuilding and Maintenance , that is planned to be established and operate next school year, near places where repair work is carried out, in the wider Piraeus Port.

e. University study paths related to Blue Economy

There are many study paths that can be applied towards work in the Blue Economy sectors. These include various Engineering degrees that can be useful in almost any sector, more so in shipbuilding, maritime transport or ocean energy and also Tourism studies where one can obtain a first Degree either in institutions of higher education or in advanced technological education institutes.

Some examples of Bachelor’s Degrees are:

- Civil engineering (NTUA, AUTH, University of Patras, University of Peloponnese, ASPETE)
- Mechanical and Electrical Engineering (AUTH, University of Thessaly, University of Applied Sciences, ASPETE)
- Environmental Engineering (Democritus University of Thrace, Technical University of Crete)
- Marine Engineering (University of West Attica)
- Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering (NTUA)

Many other qualifications can lead to being employed in the Blue Economy. Some examples are:

- Environmental science, Biology, Chemistry and Food production, Biochemistry, Biotechnology, (several Bachelor programs in Universities)
- Marine Biology (University of Thessaloniki, University of Crete)
- Oceanography and Marine Sciences (University of Aegean)

- Maritime and Transport Studies (University of Piraeus),
- Tourism Management (University of Patras),
- Fisheries & Aquaculture technology (University of Patras),
- Shipping Trade and Transport (University of the Aegean),
- Ichthyology and Aquatic Environment (University of Thessaly)
- International Trade (University of Applied Sciences) and
- Tourism studies in institutions of higher education or in advanced technological education institutes. The list is obviously non-exhaustive.

A large array of postgraduate (Master's) Degrees allows a specialization in a certain maritime-related field, e.g. in Marine and Ocean Technology and Science (NTUA, School of Naval Architecture & Marine Engineering), in International Shipping, Finance and Management (AUEB), in Sustainability and Quality in Marine Industry (University of Piraeus), in Oceanography (University of the Aegean), and in Sustainable Management of Aquatic Environment (University of Thessaly), among others.

A trans-national two-years Masters' program, called the Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree in Aquaculture, Environment and Society Plus (EMJMD ACES+) involves study periods in four different European countries (Scotland, Greece, France and the Netherlands) in order to benefit from different welfare models, teaching strengths and the experience of living in different cultures and societies.¹

Furthermore, there are numerous opportunities for participating in short courses at Bachelor, Masters and PhD level, and also summer-schools at all levels. For example, the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, the Vienna Institute of Social Ecology, Alpen Adria University and the University of Patras, have jointly organized the 3rd Summer School on the Island of Samothraki, Greece Aquatic & Social Ecology: Theory and Practice.²

1 www.emm-aces.org/?page_id=7

2 bit.ly/3AZvGOB

II. SECTORS

The Blue Economy sectors in Greece employ over 347,000 people and generates around €6 billion in GVA in 2017. Overall, Blue Economy jobs increased by 93% and GVA by 32% compared to 2009. Greece's Blue Economy is dominated by the coastal tourism sector, which contributed 77% to jobs, 56% to GVA in 2017. Maritime transport is also a large contributor, with 17% of GVA and 5% of the employment, while the living resource sector on the other hand generates 11% of the jobs but contributes only 1% to GVA.

The Blue Economy has had a significant positive impact on Greek GDP and employment. While the national GDP fell strongly (24%) between 2009 and 2017, Blue Economy GVA rose (32%).

Additionally, the percentage that the Blue Economy contributes to overall national GVA reached 3.3% in 2016, which is a 73% increase from the 2009 figure, when it stood at 1.9%.

The same can be said for jobs: where the national levels fell overall, Blue Economy-based jobs grew by approximately 93%. The share of jobs covered by the Blue Economy now amounts to around 9.4%, whereas in 2009 this figure was about 4.0%, reflecting a 134% increase. The average wage in the Greek Blue Economy in 2017 was €13,400, a 26% decrease on 2009.³

a. Coastal tourism

Coastal Tourism is a central pillar of Greek Economy, including a large variety of services and industries. Tourism is an export champion for Greece as it represents 20.6% of GDP (2018, WTTC), 25.9% of employment (WTTC) and 9% yield of hospitality real estate, one of the most competitive in Europe.⁴ The competitive advantages of Greece, such as rich cultural heritage, natural beauty and geographical variety, have been attracting significant tourism investments in recent years, thus further strengthening Greece's image as an ideal destination both for holidays and tourism-related investments.

Even during the financial crisis of the last decade, the tourism industry in Greece has been one of the mainstays of economic growth and employment, with a continued growth in tourist arrivals and revenues driven mainly by:

3 The EU Blue Economy Report 2019

4 Tourism Sector, Enterprise and Trade

- the determined efforts of Greek tourist authorities and associations to upgrade the tourist product offering
- the development of key, new markets such as Russia, Israel, Turkey and China.

The tourism industry is currently undergoing a major strategic improvement initiative, focusing on the expansion of the tourist period, the attraction of higher-value tourist segments, the increase of average daily spending and the opening of new tourist markets.

Over the next years, Greece is poised to make significant investments in the tourism industry, focused on transforming the traditional “sun & beach” tourist product into a number of higher-value, more focused products, centered around:

- Thematic sun & beach tourism,
- Nautical tourism,
- City break tourism
- Cultural and religious tourism,
- Medical tourism
- Meetings and Incentives (MICE) tourism
- Sports tourism (e.g. golf, training activities etc.),
- Integrated resorts

The country’s hotel potential has been extremely upgraded in 2019:

- The number of 5-star hotel beds increased by +75% from 2010 to 2019, while the corresponding figure of 1-star hotel beds decreased by -11% during the same period
- Greece recorded the highest overall score in the Mediterranean with 87.1%, according to the Global Review Index* 2019
- 2019 was a landmark year, as intense investment activity was recorded in the hotel industry Greece ranked 18th globally in Tourist Service Infrastructure among 140 countries, according to 2019 WEF’s Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index.

The upgrading of the tourist product is supported by a number of initiatives by the Greek state, the Greek National Tourism Organization, the relevant business associations, and the regional authorities and municipalities, and is considered to be a strategic avenue for growth in the Greek economy.

The tourism sector is organized by in various associations at national level such as:

- Greek National Tourism Organization mintour.gov.gr/en/contact/
- Greek Tourism Confederation (representing the sector’s entrepreneurs) - sete.gr/en/
- Hellenic Chamber of Hotels www.grhotels.gr/EN/Pages/default.aspx
- Hellenic Association of Tourist & Travel Agencies - www.hatta.gr/
- Hellenic Association of Professional Congress Organizers - hapco.gr/index.php/en/
- Hellenic Hoteliers Federation www.hhf.gr/about-us/
- Hellenic Yacht Brokers Association www.hyba.gr/
- Research Institute for Tourism - www.grhotels.gr/en/about-us/research-institute-for-tourism/
- Greek Marinas Association www.greek-marinas.gr/
- Secaplas - secaplas.gr/

The development of infrastructure to support nautical tourism is a strategic goal for Greece over the next years. More specifically, the Greek state has announced significant investments:

- in the upgrading of cruise port facilities so that more cruise companies will use Greek ports as home ports for their Mediterranean cruises
- in the privatization and upgrading of the state and municipality owned marinas, in order to attract more and larger yachts

Several international investors have already taken advantage of such opportunities, recognizing the great opportunity in this high-value tourist product.

Nautical tourism includes recreational boating, cruises, marinas, water sports as well as maritime history tourism, marine wildlife tourism and many other land-based related activities such as nautical museums and resorts.

The Greek port system further consists of 38 peripheral port organizations that each manage smaller ports and 1.250 municipal ports, mainly marinas, and fishing ports.

Greece is experiencing a boom in numbers of cruise ships and visitors, following the existing regulatory framework that the country implemented in order to lift cabotage rules. This has liberalized the cruise market allowing non-EU flagged cruise ships to embark passengers from Greek ports and combined with the infrastructure improvements currently planned in major Greek ports is expected

to significantly improve the number of cruise ships using Greece either as a home port or a port of call.

The main competitive advantages of the country include a great coastline, the large number of available ports - most of them close to world renowned attractions - the small distances between destinations, and the country's location - at the center of the Eastern Mediterranean Sea, one of the world's most visited regions.

b. Aquaculture

For Greece, aquaculture has been recognized as one of the main activities that can contribute to the economic recovery and create a solid base for growth in the coming years. Aquaculture in Greece is dominated by marine fish. Fish and fishery products are the country's first export for animal production. Greece is in the top two countries in Mediterranean fish farming, accounting for 24% of international production. Greece is exporting aquaculture products mainly to Italy (43%), in Spain (16%), in France (12%) and in United Kingdom (2%).⁵

Fish farming has been around for 30 years of the country's main aquaculture activity. The main species bred are sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) and sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) making up about 98% of sales, while on a much smaller scale, about 2%, all other Mediterranean species are bred, *Diplodus puntazzo*, *Pagrus pagrus*, *Pagellus erythrinus*, cranberry (*Argyrosomus Regius*), rib (*Dentex dentex*) etc. From 1981, when the first experimental units were created, the industry reached in 2016 one of the first positions worldwide in the farming of Mediterranean fish. Today, 63 companies are active with 366 units throughout Greece, where the majority are family, small and medium-sized enterprises. However, there are larger groups that own verticalized companies that, in addition to raising fish, produce offspring and food. Institutionally, the sector is represented by two associations, SETH and PANEMMI.⁶

Furthermore, Greece supports the production of organic fish farming which is done by two certified units belonging to two fish farming companies, while there are also three private Organizations of Control and Certification in the field of organic fish farming (BIOELLAS, COSMOCERT, GMCERT) which have been approved and supervised by the Hellenic Agricultural Organization "Dimitra".⁷

Fish farming creates jobs in 10 of the 13 Regions of Greece with Western Greece, Central Greece, the Peloponnese and Attica having the most jobs. It is worth noting that Greece has one of the highest employment rates of all those employed in the EU aquaculture sector.

According to the latest available data, the whole of those directly employed in the industry amounted to 4,397 permanent and temporary staff, presenting 6% increase over the previous year (2018). The increase concerns exclusively permanent jobs of specialized or non-specialized staff. Marine farming (fish and mussels) creates 83% of direct jobs, cultivation in brackish water 10%, while indoor cultivation 7% water.⁸

According to the interim evaluation of the Multiannual National Strategic Plan for aquaculture development between 2014- 2020, the average growth rate has been revised and it is estimated that between 2017-2023 it will be at 5.5% and over the next seven years will return to the initial estimate of 7% average annual growth. If this program is implemented, then in 2030 the production is expected to range to 220,000 tons.⁹

Regarding the fisheries sector, the Greek fishing fleet is characterized by a large number of fishing boats with small capacity and machine power (approximately 96%) that carry out polyhedral and multi-collection fishing along the extensive coastline of the mainland, as well as the numerous Greek islands. The Greek fishing fleet, according to the data of the National Fisheries Register in 2018, included a total of 14,123 active fishing vessels which makes the Greek professional fishing fleet the largest fishing fleet in the EU. Larger vessels have more powerful tools, such as trawlers (1.8%) and gri gris (1.7%), or are boats that have hooked tools (longlines and lines) and target large migratory species, such as tuna and swordfish and operate at greater distances from the coast or even in international waters (beyond 6 nautical miles).¹⁰

The categorization, behavior and dynamics of the country's professional fishing fleet have been integrated into the system. Since 2009, information has been provided by the Satellite Tracking Monitoring System (SPS) and concerns fishing vessels with a total length of more than 15 meters, recording their location and speed every 2 hours.¹¹

5 FGM, Kontali, 2019

6 FGM, Kontali, 2019

7 FGM, Kontali, 2016

8 FGM, Kontali, 2019

9 FGM, Kontali 2019

10 www.alieia.minagric.gr/node/8

11 www.alieia.minagric.gr/node/153

c. Maritime Transport

Shipping industry Greece is a major maritime nation with its shipping industry, along with tourism, being the most important sectors of the national economy. Greece is the 1st country worldwide regarding vessel capacity and particularly it is the 8th largest ship registry.¹² Greek shipping accounts for 53% of the European Union's fleet and almost 21% of the global fleet, according to the Hellenic Shipowners' Association. The Greek-owned fleet is the world's largest cross-trading fleet with 98% of its trading capacity carrying cargoes between third countries.

Greek shipping is the cornerstone of the EU maritime cluster, guaranteeing the presence and development of EU ancillary shipping industries and, by extension, of employment opportunities and the retention of skills, expertise and maritime know-how in the EU. This is despite the fact that many shipping activities, including ship building, have, to a very large extent, moved to the Far East. The Greek-owned fleet represents more than half of the entire EU-controlled fleet.

Greek shipowners continuously renew and expand their fleet, embracing technological developments and investing in innovative, more efficient and environmentally friendly vessels, that makes life on board for seafarers easier and safer, thus more attractive.¹³ The modern shipbuilding activities

¹² IHS Markit, World Shipping Encyclopedia, January 2019

¹³ Union of Greek Shipowners, Greek Shipping, A major EU export industry of strategic importance, 2019

started in Greece in 1965 with the establishment of the Hellenic Shipyards (Skaramagka), followed by the creation of the Elefsina Shipyards, the Chalkis Shipyards and the NEORION-Siros Shipyards. In general, the shipbuilding and ship repair were among the most important sectors of the Greek economy, in terms of turnover and employment

Moreover, Greek companies that manufacture and export marine equipment of high technological added value have decided to join forces and create HEMEXPO – Hellenic Marine Equipment Manufacturers and Exporters. HEMEXPO aims to achieve a powerful opening and potential exporting to shipyards. The association involves the larger marine equipment companies in Greece and thereby strengthens the links between the industry's leading companies through sharing of market intelligence, providing a vehicle for greater cooperation with ship-owners and shipyards.

Finally, the companies derive their competitiveness through designing and producing innovative and reliable high-quality products supplied for the building, conversion, maintenance of ships (seagoing and inland) and maritime structures.

Maritime Transport represents a significant subsector in the most important ports in Greece: Port of Piraeus, Port of Thessaloniki, Port of Patras, Port of Corfu, Port of Kavala, Port of Alexandroupoli, Port of Volos, Port of Heraklion, Port of Rhodes, Port of Rafina and Port of Igoumenitsa. The Greek port system primarily consists of 12 major state-owned ports, including the country's two main key ports, Piraeus and Thessaloniki, and 10 ports of national interest (Alexandroupoli, Elefsina, Heraklion, Igoumenitsa, Kavala, Kerkyra, Lavrio, Patra, Rafina and Volos). The Greek port system further consists of 38 peripheral port organizations that each manage smaller ports and 1.250 municipal ports, mainly marinas, and fishing ports.

d. Marine Biotechnology

There are no specific Marine Biotechnology strategies, plans or policies in Greece. The general orientation of scientific research is provided by an overarching Strategy for Research, Technology and Innovation. The marine and biotechnology research components are not further elaborated in a policy or strategy. The Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR) is a governmental research organization operating under the supervision of the General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) of the Ministry of Education, Research and Religious Affairs and it has three

institutes related to marine biotechnology and resources.¹⁴

In Greece, offshore wind farms are governed by the law on renewable energy sources, but there are no installed wind parks and tidal systems do not apply in Greece as the eastern Mediterranean Sea is non-tidal. The new technology of offshore windfarms is hindered in Greece by has many areas with great sea depth, with the consequence that there are limited sea-spaces that can support the installation of such developments. Nevertheless, there has been interest and the sea wind capacity is high, mainly in the Aegean Sea.

III. PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The established sectors such as coastal tourism, fisheries and aquaculture, maritime transport and shipbuilding have national and regional administrative departments.

The coastal tourism sector is represented by the Ministry of Tourism. The mission of the Ministry of Tourism is the planning and drawing up of the tourist policy as well as the planning of the tourism development of the country. The responsibilities of the Ministry of Tourism include the supervision of the operation of the following tourism agencies: Greek Tourism Organization and Hotel Chamber of Greece.

The maritime transport and shipbuilding sectors are under the responsibility of the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Insular Policy. The Ministry is on the one hand the administrative body of the Merchant Shipping, and on the other hand, through the Hellenic Coast Guard, its mission is to implement the law in maritime areas, on ships and vessels of all kinds and in shipbuilding, as well as on land, in coastal or marine areas.

The following General Secretariats are under the Ministry of Shipping and Island Policy:

- General Secretariat for Shipping and Island Policy
- General Secretariat of Ports, Port Policy & Shipping Investments
- General Secretariat for the Aegean and Island Policy

The Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Insular Policy together with the three General Secretariats provide public services for the rescue of human life at sea, and for the protection of the marine environment, as well as ensuring compliance and controlling the implementation of maritime safety rules on ships and port facilities, and the terms of safe ship management. Other responsibilities are the administrative supervision of maritime transport as well as the supervision, administration and exploitation of Greek ports, shipping infrastructure, shipyards, etc.

For fisheries and aquaculture, the General Directorate of Fisheries is the administrative department of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food, which manages the fisheries, aquaculture and trade-processing sectors of fishery products. It has the strategic goal of promoting the primary sector through the development of cooperative fisheries and aquaculture, with the aim of optimally managing fisheries resources, implementing control of activities and promoting actions within the EU and International Organizations.

There are no specific Marine Biotechnology strategies, plans or policies in Greece. General orientation of scientific research is provided by an overarching Strategy for Research, Technology and Innovation in the context of the National Strategic Reference Framework of the General Secretariat for Research & Technology. The marine and biotechnology research components are not further elaborated in a policy or strategy. Greece is a member-state of the European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC) by the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR). HCMR comprises three institutes, one of which is part of EMBRC: Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC). MBBC has been recognized as a center of excellence in marine biodiversity and conducts research at all levels of biological organization, from genes to ecosystems.

The Ministry of Environment and Energy is responsible for the Greek energy market taking into account the adaptation and harmonization with modern international developments related to ocean energy. The other relevant public body depending on this ministry is the General of Energy, with responsibility for the supervision of the Directorate of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and Alternative Fuel and the Directorate of Energy Policies and Energy Efficiency.

14 Marine Biotechnology, ERA - NET, 2019

IV. PLACEMENT AGENCIES

The Greek Manpower Employment Organization (OAED) is a legal entity operating under the supervision of the Minister of Labour and Social Affairs.

OAED consists of the following units/services:

- The Head Office (Central Administration) which consists of three General Directorates and seven Regional Directorates. The Regional Directorates supervise the operation of the local units and services.
- A network of one hundred and eighteen (118) local Public Employment Services offices and a number of educational institutions.

In addition, a large array of NGOs and Private Foundations/Organizations, i.e. knowl social enterprise for lifelong learning, Odyssea, The Athens Global Shapers Hub and many others, who work with youth an especially NEETs at national and regional level, promoting youth employment, offering mentoring, helping young job seekers at national and regional level and connecting them directly with the job market.

V. PROMOTIONAL VISITS

The promotional visits for the working opportunities in the Blue Economy require a rather unique approach for each different target group of the BlueGeneration project. The project is aimed at young people aged 15-29 who are not employed, do not study, are not professionally trained and in addition have stopped looking for work (NEETs). The circles of awareness and attraction of young people are carried out in a wide range of bodies and organizations of the public, private and third sectors of the economy in the fields of education, training, the fight against unemployment and the support of employment in Greece.

Typical groups of young people in Greece, depending on the studies, age and employment are:

- Young people that are finishing mandatory secondary school (15-16 years old) and high school (17-18 years old). These youths are found in public and private high schools. They require more general information about the Blue Economy and its sub-sectors and the careers opportunities
- Vocational High schools and specific VET training centres have mainly students (16-18 years old and 18+ years old) that are more

interested in careers opportunities, mentoring and job placement, for their specific field of study, e.g. VET students of Tourism might want information about cruise ships or VET student of mechanical engineering are interested in Leisure Boat Maintenance

- Students at Universities in the age group from 18-25, are interested in career opportunities, mentoring and job placement in their specific field of study and how they can adapt their field of study into the Blue Economy. They are also interested in internships and job opportunities abroad
- Young disadvantaged people (inactive youth living with parents, young mothers and young people with drug or alcohol abuse) than can be found at various NGOs, and are more interested in job offers with a low academic profile, training options and dual VET
- In placement agencies, young unemployed people are more interested in seeking for a job and through the Blue Career Job Platform
- Youth at adult education centres (18+ years old) are more interested in counselling and job opportunities with a low academic profile.

To reach young people, various communication methods are in place:

For young people who have not finished their current education (15 - 19 years old), it is needed to get a special permission to access schools from the Ministry of Education in Greece. Until such license was secured, pilot actions with Secondary Education Directorates mainly in the region of Attica were conducted. The General Secretary of Lifelong Learning, which informed the public and private VET centers of Greece as well as Secondary Schools about implementing a promotional visit, is another essential gateway to achieving large-scale contacts. Direct communications with the careers service officials of Universities have resulted in high interest and willingness to host such promotional meetings.

Communication towards this aim was extended to the Regions and Municipalities officers in an attempt to reach young people aged 15-29 in collaboration with Unemployment Offices and state-run youth centers. Youth centers supported by NGOs who work with youth people (especially NEETs) are contacted directly.

The Greek Manpower Employment Organization (OAED) was named an Associate Partner and supports our project as well.

Country Report **Poland**

I. TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES

Several opportunities for acquiring academic proficiency or professional training related to the different Blue Economy sub-sectors are offered in Poland. Professional high schools (Szkoły Branżowe in Polish), public and private universities offer various types of higher and VET education.

a. VET Training

The most popular Vocational Training institutions and courses are:

1 Zespół Szkół Morskich w Darłowie¹ (Maritime Schools Association) which offers education as:

- Officer of sea navigation
- Officer of logistics
- Mechanic - Technician
- Technician of hotel business

1 www.zsm.darlowo.pl

2 Zespół Szkół Morskich w Kołobrzegu² (Maritime Schools Association) which offers education as:

- Technician of sea navigation
- Technician of logistics
- Mechanic - Technician

3 Technikum Żeglugi Śródlądowej we Wrocławiu³ (Inland Sailing VET) which offers education for technicians of inland sailing

4 Technikum Budowy Okrętów Gdynia⁴ (Ship Building VET) which offers education as:

- Technician of ship building
- Technician of docks and ports maintenance
- Mechanic - Technician

2 www.zsmor.pl/

3 tzs.edu.pl/

4 ckziu1gdynia.wixsite.com/ckziu1gdynia

All VET schools are dedicated to students who recently graduated primary schools.⁵ They receive vocational education on a middle level and after graduation and passing the exams hold the qualification of a formal profession of technician. The majority of Polish VET schools is public and free of charge.

b. University studies

On the level of Higher Education Polish universities offer a range of studies related to blue economy:

- 1) **Tourism** related activities or Tourism Management (bachelor and master studies):
 - a) Tourism and leisure:
 - i) Silesian University in Katowice - us.edu.pl/
 - ii) Wrocław University in Wrocław - rekrutacja.uni.wroc.pl/
 - iii) Main School of Tourism and Hotel Industry „VISTULA” in Warszawa
 - b) Tourism management:
 - i) Łódź University in Łódź rekrutacja.uni.lodz.pl/index.php
 - ii) Higher School of Management in Warszawa - wsm.warszawa.pl/
- 2) **Aquaculture**
 - i) Aquaculture – business and technology – Gdańsk University in Gdańsk - ug.edu.pl/
 - ii) National Marine Fisheries Research Institute in Gdynia - mir.gdynia.pl/
- 3) **Biotechnology**
 - i) Jagiellonian University in Kraków - www.uj.edu.pl/
 - ii) Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań - amu.edu.pl/kandydaci
 - iii) Silesian University of Technology in Gliwice - www.polsl.pl/Strony/Witamy.aspx
 - iv) University of Gdansk (Oceanography and Geography Department) offers a two-year MSc program in Biological Oceanography with a specialization in marine biotechnology – www.geo.ug.edu.pl

For **Maritime Transport** one of the most popular Polish universities and also the one which offers the largest number of faculties related to the Blue

Economy, is the Maritime University in Gdynia: umg.edu.pl/en/. The following training courses are offered by this public University:

- i) Marine Engineering
- ii) Offshore Technologies
- iii) Maritime Transport and Logistics Systems, and other.

The Maritime Academy in Szczecin⁶ is very popular among students. Besides Mechatronics and Ship Building it also offers a Master degree as inland sailing officer.

Both maritime high schools also offer training courses to become a lifeguard, a ship crew member or even a navy officer.

Additionally, Poland has a network of training centres that provide free complementary education for adults, the most popular network is Zakład Doskonalenia Zawodowego⁷ (The Union of Vocational Education Centres). These study centres can be found in every big city of Poland and most training centres in Northern Poland offer courses related to the Blue Economy, including for professions such as:

- Navy officer
- Pipeline engineer
- Electrical engineer
- Tourism and Recreation
- Welder
- Electrical fitter

II. SECTORS

The Polish Blue Economy employs over 120.000 people and generates around 28,5 billion in GVA. It is dominated by shipbuilding and the coastal tourism sector, which contributed 75 000 to Blue Economy jobs in 2021. The living resources sector, fisheries and aquaculture, is also an important contributor, with 29.000 of jobs.

Shipbuilding is mostly related to the shipyard in Gdańsk (Stocznia Gdańska), because of its historical value. It was the area where workers first rose-up against communistic oppression and the „Solidarność” movement was born. Thanks to this event, the shipyard is now known to each and

⁵ ckziu1gdynia.wixsite.com/ckziu1gdynia

⁶ www.am.szczecin.pl/pl/

⁷ zzdz.pl/

every Pole. There is also a well-known shipyard in Szczecin. A lot of specialist are required in this industry: designers, engineers, carpenters, welders, electricians.

The second biggest sector is **Coastal Tourism**, established along the 770 kilometers long coastline of the Polish Baltic Sea. Cities like Międzyzdroje or Władysławowo are very popular holiday destinations. Coastal Tourism in Poland is very seasonal due to the Baltic climate, nevertheless, it offers a wide variety of employment and business opportunities in hotels, restaurants, bars and cafés. Managers, Administrative staff, waiters, cooks, clerks, room service workers, etc. are needed especially in the summer months.

A newly developing part of **Coastal Tourism** in Poland is the Nautical Tourism. This includes the building of motor boats, sailing yachts, catamarans and other recreational vessels in already 115 boatyards such as Galeon or Sunreef Yachts⁸. Connected to this industry are supporting services that produce parts, offer boat maintenance, marina services and charter/ skipper services.

Higher education for Nautical Tourism is offered by Wyższa Szkoła Bezpieczeństwa⁹ (Higher School of Safety) that provides Safety in Nautical Tourism studies.

Maritime Transport offers opportunities to captains, officers and engineers in ferry companies such as Stena Line and Polferries in coastal and international waters; inland shipping is well developed on Poland's major rivers.

8 bit.ly/3AXDnFd

9 bit.ly/3R5XmHc

Another, also very popular sector, is **Fisheries**.

Annelies Ilena, believed to be one of the biggest trawlers in the world, is registered in Poland. Companies like Superfish, Linser or Frosta are well known for this sector.

Currently, Poland is becoming more environmentally friendly. Solar panels and other renewable energy sources are getting more and more popular. The **Ocean Energy** sector, although currently still only existent in the research and development phase, is predicted to be growing rapidly is estimated to generate a lot of new job placements in next 5 years.

Some of companies related to Blue Economy have established their own associations:

- Polish Maritime Technology Forum – associates companies from wide range of profession related to Blue Economy
- Polish Association of Wind Energy – associates power producers
- Polish Association of Fish Processing associates companies producing fishes related food
- Cutter Shipowners Association
- Polish Maritime Foundation
- Pomeria Federation of Scientific and Technical Associations

III. PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The Ministry of Maritime Economy and Inland Sailing is the most important public administration institution related to Blue Economy Sectors. Under its jurisdiction are fields such as:

- maritime transport and infrastructure development;
- protection and rational usage of marine resources;
- planning and management of Polish marine territories;
- flood protection;
- hydrology;
- ports, docks and ships protection;
- fresh water consumption policy;
- The Baltic Sea protection;
- marine policy management;
- marine education
- international marine policy and cooperation;

Also very important government agency is Polish Waters. It's mission is to:

- prevent from droughts and floodings
- water resources maintenance and protection
- provide good quality of water for current and next generations
- providing water to Polish citizens and companies

Local government institutions connected to the Blue Economy protect and develop regions, including the Blue Economy education and labour market. The 16 provinces, 380 counties and 2.477 municipalities work together to create and provide new opportunities for people.

Climate change is showing its effects in Poland which is becoming one of the biggest challenges the government and local authorities are facing. Long-term strategies are being reviewed and include the revival of inland shipping, which was once the most popular transport system in Poland but has become non-existent.

IV. PLACEMENT AGENCIES

The biggest placement agencies in Poland are:

- Randstad www.randstad.pl/
- Work Service www.workservice.pl/
- Adecco www.adecco.pl/
- Manpower www.manpower.pl/
- Trenkwalder pl.trenkwalder.com/
- Interkadra www.interkadra.pl/
- Jobimpulse jobimpulse.pl/
- Gi Group pl.gigroup.com/

All placement agencies can be found in the state registry:

stor.praca.gov.pl/portal/#/kraz/wyszukiwarka

The most popular way to find a job or look for an employee is through the official labour offices. They can be found in every city that is a capital of district called 'powiat' in Poland.

Young people who are NEETs can also use help which is offered by Voluntary Labour Corps (Ochotnicze Hufce Pracy). The Voluntary Labour Corps is a state-run organizational unit working to prevent the social exclusion of young people. In line with the current Act on Employment Promotion and Labour Market Institutions, the Voluntary Labour Corps is a labour market institution supervised by the Minister of Family, Labour and Social Policy that performs state tasks directed towards teenagers over 15 years of age, and the unemployed under 25 years of age. Those tasks include employment services, counteract social marginalization and social exclusion, as well as tasks related to education and upbringing.

Their branches can be found in 49 Polish cities: bit.ly/3RmEWBW

This link also includes most NGO's that work with young unemployed people and which are associated in a network called Nongovernmental Labour Market Institution. This network consists of more than 150 members.

V. PROMOTIONAL VISITS

The Region of Silesia, which is the area where the BlueGeneration Project was first implemented in Poland, is mostly known for its coal mining industry. It is located in the southern part of the country, about 500km away from the nearest Baltic Sea coast. The Blue Economy is therefore not well known or popular in this region, although Silesia has a lot of historical connections to these sectors: The biggest inland dock in Europe is located in Gliwice. It used to be used for river transport in XIX and XX century. Forgotten for a long time, inland river transport is returning. The Vistula and Odra rivers are planned to become alternatives to heavy lorry transport directed to the Baltic Sea. This creates a lot of opportunities for young people's future professional career and is being promoted to young people in the frame of the BlueGeneration Program.

Promotional activities, mostly in the Silesia Region in southern Poland and in Łódzkie Region in central Poland were directed at:

- a) High schools (here especially targeting school principals and career advisors):
 - Mechanical-Engineering High School in Rybnik
 - Economical-Gastronomic High School in Oświęcim

- Economical-Gastronomic High School in Wola
 - Grammar School in Gilowice
 - Grammar School in Łódź
 - Grammar School in Łowicz
- b) Public labour market institutions
 - Labour office of Rybnik district
 - Labour office of Łódź region
 - c) Two Silesian universities
 - d) VET centers
 - e) NGO's working in labour insertion
 - f) NEETS in general – brought together in the First National Seminar in Katowice, Silesia Region, Poland.
 - g) All stakeholders through the BlueGeneration Poland Facebook page;

These promotional visits reached young people who are looking to start their professional career, especially the following groups:

- Students and pupils
- Young adults
- NEET's (not in employment, education or training)

Country Report **Portugal**

I. TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES

This document contains the training opportunities related with the Blue Economy regarding School and University Education and National Agencies for employment.

In Portugal the education and training system is structured as following:

1. Primary and Secondary Education

Basic education lasts for nine years starting at the age of 6 and is divided into three stages of four, two and three years respectively. After each stage the student will receive a certification at a national level which will allow him/her to choose between general courses and technical/vocational courses for the final stage.

For the scope of this guide, only the technical/vocational courses related to the blue economy (named in Portugal as Certificado de Habilitações do Ensino Secundário/Diploma de Ensino Secundário) will be presented. These will allow the students to submit an application for the higher education such as Academic degrees.

According to the Ministry of Education a high percentage of students are enrolled in technical/vocational courses: Vocational Courses (33.3%),

Apprenticeship Courses (6.2%), Education and Training Courses (CEF) (0.1%)¹ data for the year 2017/2018.

2. Higher education

The Higher education in Portugal is divided into two subsystems: university education and non-university higher education (polytechnic education) and they are following the Bologna system.²

The Portuguese education structures in line with the European Qualification Framework are:

- Level 5 including VET centers qualifications
- Level 6 known as Bachelor degree integrated in the higher education
- Level 7 for specialized professionals in Blue Economy field with a Master degree

The geographical position of Portugal represents a big advantage in training and specializing young people in the Blue Economy with a variety of universities expanded in different regions of the country.

1 Statistical data collected by DGEEC/MEC "Educação em números - Portugal 2019

2 www.euroeducation.net/prof/porco.htm

The main specialties the young people can enroll during the academic studies related to the Blue Economy are the following:

1. Centro de Engenharia e Tecnologia Naval e Oceânica	Ship Design and Shipbuilding Maritime Transportation and Ports
2. Escola Superior Náutica Infante Dom Henrique, Lisbon	Bachelor (Portuguese: licentiate) and master programs in: Pilotage; Marine Marines Engineering, Marine Electronic Systems, Port Management;
3. Maritime Academy Portugal	Certification of maritime education and training providers
4. National Focal Point	Education, Scholarships, Apprenticeships and Youth Entrepreneurships in Blue Economy
5. Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa	Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering
6. Universidade do Algarve	Marine and Coastal Management/ Marine Biology
7. The World of Shipping Portugal Training Program	Training Programs covers the areas of Distribution Channels and Logistics, Maritime Economics, and Maritime and Logistics English
8. School of Law Universidade Nova de Lisboa	Master in Law and Ocean Economy
9. ISEG- Lisbon School of Economics & Management	Post Graduation in Shipping and Port Management

Additionally:

CIIMAR - Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research - is a research and advanced training institution hosted

by the University of Porto. Its mission is to develop exceptional-quality research, promote technological development and support public policies in the area of Marine and Environmental Sciences.

The “Blue Biotechnology Master for a Blue Career” (BBMBC) is a European project co-funded by the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) in the framework of the European Integrated Maritime Policy³. Participating countries are France, Spain, United Kingdom, and Portugal.

VET Centers

- 1 Instituto de Tecnologias Náuticas – QNQ Level 4 and STCW Qualification | Maritime Transports | itn.com.pt
- 2 FORMAR – QNQ | Level 4 | Fisheries and Maritime Transports | for-mar.pt
- 3 Escola Profissional de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa – QNQ | Level 4 | Tourism | www.ephtl.edu.pt
- 4 Escolas Turismo de Portugal – QNQ | Level 4 and 5 | escolas.turismodeportugal.pt/

II. SECTORS

Portugal, due to its geographical position, is one of the most important European countries for the Blue Economy with a coastline length 2.600 km (including the Atlantic islands of Madeira and Azores), which is expanding from the north to the south and is playing a big role in the regional and national economy.

The main Blue Economy sub-sectors in Portugal are the following:

Coastal tourism represents an important sector for Portugal’s economy and the support of the government has had a big impact on the growth of this sector which helped Portugal to become repeatedly awarded as a Leading Destination⁴. Coastal Tourism in Portugal has generated 5.7 billion Euros in 2020, which represents 12% of the European income from the Coastal Tourism sector. It employs 212.000 persons in nautical activities and Marine Tourism, Hospitality and Leisure.

Aquaculture is a growing sector with over 2.000 employees and a GVA of around 100 million € in

4 www.worldtravelawards.com/

2020⁵. The governmental institution responsible for Aquaculture in Portugal is The Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services (DGRM) which developed the Strategic Plan for Portuguese Aquaculture (2014-2020)⁶ to support a sustainable growth in the future.

Marine Biotechnology: Portugal released in 2019 its Blue Bioeconomy Roadmap⁷ 2030 that envisages that by 2030 Portugal's economy will be more competitive, with a focus on sustainable innovation and will be at the forefront of the Blue Bioeconomy in Europe.

Its main association involved in the growth of this sector is the P-BIO Portugal's Biotechnology Industry Organization⁸.

Additionally, the **BLUEBIO ALLIANCE (BBA)** is a national network that includes all subsectors of the marine bioresources value chain in Portugal, incl. fisheries, aquaculture and marine biotechnology. It ranges from raw material producers, R&D units, to biotech SMEs, transforming centers and manufacturers, public sector entities and support companies, up to the final consumer product developers⁹.

Shipbuilding and Maintenance is considered an important sector with more than 200 shipbuilding and repair companies in Portugal. The main association present in Portugal for shipbuilding, maintenance and repair is **AIN** (Associação das Indústrias Navais) - The Association of Portuguese Maritime Industries is an Employers Association, with the main objective of representing shipbuilding and ship repair, and a diversified number of companies operating in related fields, notably, consulting services, equipment suppliers and maritime-harbour operators. AIN represents a large diversity of members, ranging from the maintenance of the largest merchant marine ships or the construction of complex ships, maintenance of the Navy fleet, up to the small units for leisure or fishing. The shipyard members of AIN represent in terms of sales volume around 85 % of total Portuguese shipbuilding and ship repair turnover. The Association is the Sectorial Body for shipbuilding standardisation by delegation of the Portuguese National Standardisation Body.

5 bit.ly/3ReK76W

6 bit.ly/3CJQOdd

7 bit.ly/3CL2o7O

8 p-bio.org/en/

9 www.bluebioalliance.pt/

In **Maritime Transport** APP – Associação dos Portos is the umbrella organization that manages the biggest ports in Portugal and is in charge of the strategy in this field. There are also smaller associations who are running different projects to solve punctual problems in the sector such as Petrosport organizing international conferences for professionals, YoungShip Portugal and European International Shipowners Association of Portugal (EISAP). Since this sector marked its importance as a resource in Portugal, scientists are also involved in research and developing new strategies, e.g. EurOcean specializes in Marine Knowledge Management, Marine Research Infrastructures and Ocean Public Outreach and Awareness activities.

Marine Environment Conservation started to gain more influence in Portugal in recent years with the direct support of the government. In this context many organizations got involved in fighting for the protection of the marine ecosystems and professionals such as scientists are working in research programs to develop a sustainable environment for both the companies working in this field and the marine life. Currently there are several NGOs in Portugal working together in international and national projects to make an impact, for example: Grupo de Estudos de Ordenamento do Território e Ambiente, Liga para a Protecção da Natureza, Quercus and Sciaena are working internationally under the umbrella association Seas At Risk. Other important organizations acting on local and regional level are Oceans Blue Heart CRL in Lisbon, CENTRE FOR MARINE SCIENCES (CCMAR) in Faro, Marine Environment Research Association, Oceano Azul Foundation.

Ocean Energy represents a subsector in the field of Renewable Energy which has gained a lot of interest and support from the government. Currently the renewable energy sources represent 69, 9% of the electricity production mix in Portugal and whilst inland Hydropower delivers about a third of this renewable energy, the umbrella association for this Portuguese Renewable Energy Association (APREN) reported that currently no ocean energy is being produced in Portugal.¹⁰

The Portuguese Maritime sector also has very engaged NGOs, such as the Fórum Oceano – Associação da Economia do Mar¹¹ which focuses

10 www.apren.pt/en/apren/about-us

11 www.forumoceano.pt/p28-association-en

on increasing the maritime economy whilst contributing, in a sustainable way, to economic growth and the growth of exports and employment.

The Bluetech Accelerator was created as a networking and cooperation space for Startups in the Blue Economy, financed by the government and EEA Grants.

III. PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

Coastal tourism since it represents an important factor in Portugal's economy has a national and regional representation in the government. On the national level, it is represented in the Ministry of Economy by the Secretary of State of Tourism. On a regional and local level, administrations collaborate with different associations who supervise and implement projects such as Grupos de Ação Local Costeiros.

For the **aquaculture** the ministry in charge is the Minister of Maritime Affairs represented by the Secretary of State for Fisheries. At local and regional level different general assemblies are responsible to manage the activities in this sector that are coordinated by the DGRM - Direção-Geral de Recursos Naturais, Segurança e Serviços Marítimos.

On regional level, Portugal has different regional directors separated in order to cover different activities conducted inside this sector for example the Direções Regionais de Agricultura e Pescas; Direção de Serviços de Planeamento e Economia Pesqueira da Direção Regional das Pescas da Região Autónoma dos Açores; Direção Regional de Pescas da Região Autónoma da Madeira.

Ship Building and Maintenance is also managed at the national level by the Minister of Economy by the Secretary of State of Industry. The enterprises that operate in Portugal in this sector receive technical and financial support from part of the Institute for the Support of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (IAPMEI) which also supervises the implementation of European regulations.

Marine environment conservation represents an important priority in Portugal since it is a major resource. The Ministry of the Sea supervises at national level the implementation of different policies and regulations to create a sustainable approach to exploit these resources; this policy has gained more importance in recent years.

IV. PLACEMENT AGENCIES

The Institute for Employment and Vocational Training is the Portuguese public employment service and was established in 1979. It works under the auspices of the Ministry of Solidarity, Employment and Social Security, being responsible for implementing the employment and vocational training policies defined and approved by the Government.

More centralized opportunities for Blue Economy can be found in the government website: bit.ly/35GABCW and on the main website for employment: www.iefp.pt/.

The 5 Regional Delegations (Norte, Centro, Lisboa e Vale Tejo, Alentejo and Algarve) distributed throughout the country in accordance with the regions set up by the Regional Coordination Commissions incorporate 86 Job Centers, 31 Directly Managed Vocational Training Centers, 1 Vocational Rehabilitation Centre - **Centro de Formação e de Reabilitação Profissional de Alcoitão** - and 8 Business Creation Support Centers.

Portugal is running on a national the following programs to support and increase the integration of youth into the workforce.

Garantia Jovem - www.garantiajovem.pt/

Emprego Jovem Ativo - bit.ly/3fsC7NH

INOV Contacto - bit.ly/3bm8cU8

Investe Jovem - bit.ly/2Lc9BBU

Estágios Profissionais - bit.ly/2yGK7d7

Estágios ATIVAR.PT - bit.ly/3gMtEpw

Incentivo ATIVAR.PT - bit.ly/2Lud9CN

StartUP Voucher - bit.ly/3nv9UJL

Emprego Interior MAIS - bit.ly/37eqTdk

V. PROMOTIONAL VISITS

The implementation of BlueGeneration Project in Portugal started by identifying and connecting with stakeholders in the field of blue economy, in order to present the best local opportunities for youth.

We established a collaboration protocol with “Blue School”, an educational program of the Portuguese Ministry of Economy and Sea, which allowed us to reach a network of schools and universities to promote the Project and attract youth for this promising area.

We have also established collaboration with Portuguese Institute of the Sea and Atmosphere, with internships in the fields of the sea and fisheries.

We also have a partnership with Blue Bio Alliance, a Portuguese network for Marine Bioresources and Biotech, which represents all players in the marine bioresources and blue biotech value chain.

With these contacts, we could reach our target group – youth from 15 to 18 years old, following Upper Secondary Education (level 3) and students enrolled in public and private Universities, from 18 and 29 years old - and present them with real opportunities, on a national and European level, when introducing the project.

Regarding students from VET centers, part of the postsecondary non-higher education, we thought it was relevant to adapt the promotional visits to their field of studies, meeting with great interest from teachers and students in areas related to tourism and event management.

Programa Escolhas, from the High Commissioner for Migration, and the Portuguese Council for Refugees, were important partners to reach youth that are not studying or working.

Contact details for educational services can be found in:

- Programa Qualifica, an adults qualification program that aims to improve the levels of education and training of adults. The list of Qualifica centers can be found in www.qualifica.gov.pt
- The Institute of Employment and Training is a national public employment service, which offers training and job opportunities. Here you can know more about the “Garantia Jovem” initiative, with specific information about active youth employment programs.
- In the General Direction of Higher Education website - www.dges.gov.pt/guias, there is a list of all the higher courses existing in Portugal.

Country Report **Romania**

I. TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES

With its opening to the Black Sea, Romania possesses several types of education for careers in the Blue Economy from VET Schools, Post-secondary education, Universities and Academies, Training Centres and other Employment companies in the economic field.

Overview of the national education and training system

In Romania, Primary, Lower Secondary and first two years of Upper Secondary Education (9th and 10th grade) are compulsory (11 years in total). According to Lower Secondary Education (gymnasium), pupils continue their studies in Upper Secondary Education: theoretical, vocational or technological education. To enrol, students must present their grade point average obtained in mathematics and Romanian language at the end of the National Assessment in 8th grade, the Lower Secondary school leaving certificate and the school report with the final grades in all subjects. The national examinations comprise language and Romanian literature, mother language (if

different from Romanian) and mathematics. If the number of places offered is less than the number of applications from secondary school graduates, vocational schools may organise entrance exams. Higher education does not include vocational education programs. However, some bachelor's and master's programs are more oriented towards practical/technical than others. For enrolment in Higher Education, all Upper Secondary school graduates must pass the baccalaureate examination. Around the age of 14, when entering high school, students can choose the Vocational Education and Training (VET) system and the professional specialisation they want to pursue. Thus, we see that the specific note for compulsory education remains the fact of keeping children in the school system until they enter the labour market. Moral and legal arguments prevail in the organisation of compulsory education, and these are overridden by pedagogical ones. The dominant objective of compulsory education is to provide the necessary level of education for integration into society. Permanent education includes a set of forms and modalities intended to train, qualify and retrain adults for professional conversion.

The education system thus includes all the specialised institutions and the network of educational organisations. In the design and implementation, by means of appropriate concepts and methodologies, of the defining functions of education. These institutions can be grouped, according to the type of education practised, into three distinct categories:

- Institutions specialised in formal education - Primary Schools, Lower Secondary Schools, Vocational Schools, Secondary Schools, University Colleges, Faculties and lifelong learning, retraining and further training units
- Institutions specialised in non-formal education - scientific circles, students' clubs, camps, vocational training centres
- Institutional agencies of the local educational community family/community of parents, economic, cultural agencies

Vocational Training is provided for 300+ professions. The practical training is carried out in the first years in school workshops operating in the educational establishments, with the possible assistance of an enterprise directly interested in the training of students, and in the last years, dedicated to specialisation and qualification, directly in economic establishments, with the performance of specific work tasks.

The main levels of structuring the education system are:

- 1 Primary Education Level
 - Pre-school educational level
 - Primary education stage (1st-4th grade)
- 2 Secondary Education Level
 - Lower Secondary Education: Gymnasium (5th-8th grade)
 - Upper Secondary Level: Secondary school/ High School (9th-12th grade)
 - Vocational: 1-2 year vocational schools for simple trades and 2-3 years vocational schools for complex professions
- 3 Higher Education Level
 - Short Higher Education Stage: 2-3 years
 - Long Higher Education Stage: 4-6 years
 - Post-graduate Higher Education Stage (advanced studies, master, doctorate)¹

1 bit.ly/3q0dGxn

VET education

Vocational qualifications acquired through vocational and technical education within initial vocational education and training (excluding vocational programs) are based on vocational training standards. The National Qualifications Register currently contains 131 EQF level 3 qualifications, 69 EQF level 4 qualifications and 203 EQF level 5 qualifications.² The vocational training standards describe the learning units consisting of learning outcomes and are based on occupational standards. Standards are developed by representatives of companies in the sectors and VET providers, with the methodological support of the National Centre for Development of Vocational and Technical Education, endorsed by the National Authority for Qualifications. They are validated by employers and other social partners through sectoral committees. The standards are reviewed at least once every five years or at the request of economic operators.

As a member state of the European Union, Romania actively contributes to the realisation of the Strategic Framework for European Cooperation in Vocational Education and Training through hundreds of vocational programs in Upper Secondary education. These students will become certificated workers in technical fields such as mechanics, electrical engineering, tourism, gastronomy and many more. Students who choose this form of education benefit from professional scholarships.

Students who want to attend a VET school or a technological high school can find out about educational establishments both in their home area and those operating nationwide using this [map](#). Parents and pupils can also find out what trades and qualifications those schools are training, as well as possible job opportunities in the field they are looking for, according to the Ministry of Education.

Authorisation of **Continuing Vocational Training** providers is coordinated by the Ministry of Labour and Social Justice. It is carried out through county authorisation commissions and gives continuing vocational training providers the right to issue qualification or graduation certificates with national recognition.

2 Vocational education and training in Romania: short description (Educația și formarea profesională în România: descriere succintă), European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training, Luxembourg Publications Office, 2019, p.56-57

EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENT	SPECIALISATION OF FACULTIES	BACHELOR	MASTER
1. Constanta Maritime University	Faculty of Marine Engineering & Faculty of Navigation and Naval Transport	Navigation and Waterborne Transport (in English)	Engineering and Management in Transport Engineering and Management in Maritime and Multimodal Transport Offshore Oil and Gas Technology and Management (in English) Management of Integrated Transport Systems Engineering and Management in Maritime & Port Fields
2. "Mircea cel Batran" Naval Academy	Faculty of Marine Engineering & Faculty of Navigation and Naval Transport	Marine Engineering and Navigation Electrical Engineering Marine Engineering and Navigation Engineering and Management	Naval Electromechanical Systems Nautical Sciences Naval and Port Engineering and Management Logistic Systems Management
3. Ovidius University of Constanta	Faculty of Mechanical, Industrial and Marine Engineering Faculty of Construction Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences Faculty of Applied Sciences and Engineering Faculty of Law and Administrative Sciences	Petroleum processing and petrochemicals Food chemistry and biochemical technologies Technological Physics Ecology and environmental protection Geography of tourism Biology Hydro-engineering and construction Civil, industrial and agricultural construction Naval systems and equipment Port and marine installations and equipment Industrial energy Economic engineering in the mechanical field	Oil processing technologies and management Renewable energy systems engineering Biodiversity preservation Coastal engineering Engineering of hydrotechnical systems Engineering and management of water resources Engineering and management of naval systems and equipment Quality and certification in welded constructions Optimisation of port technologies and machinery operation Maritime law Transport safety legislation
4. "Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati	Faculty of Engineering Faculty of Naval Architecture Faculty of Automation, Computers, Electrical Engineering and Electronics Faculty of Science and Food Engineering Faculty of Science and Environment Faculty of Economics and Business Administration Faculty Cross-Border	Efficient use of energy and renewable sources Modelling and simulation in mechanical engineering Biotechnology of natural resources Naval Architecture Engineering and management in catering and agritourism Quality management in industrial engineering Evaluation of physico-chemical and biodiversity parameters of the environment	Fish farming and aquaculture Biotechnologies for the food industry Fisheries and fish processing Electromechanics Environmental quality and sustainable development Hydrotechnical engineering and environmental protection Naval systems and equipment Naval architecture
5. Oil and Gas University of Ploiesti	Faculty of Oil-Gas Engineering Faculty of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering Faculty of Oil Refining and Petrochemistry	Hydrocarbons Transportation, Storage and Distribution Oil and Gas Engineering Engineering of Petroleum Resources Geology Petroleum and Petrochemical Equipment Petroleum Processing and Petrochemistry Chemical and Biochemical Processes Informatics and Engineering Food Control and Security	Petroleum Engineering Risk Management and Engineering Reliability of Petroleum and Petrochemical Equipment Engineering Optimal Exploitation of Oilfield Equipment Management and Production Engineering Equipment Oil and Petrochemical Petroleum Geology Computer Aided Chemical Engineering Applied in Refineries and Petrochemistry

Introduction of **dual education** in Vocational Training Programs in 2017/18 was aimed at adapting the training vocational training to better meet the needs of employers. Its expansion to EQF levels 4 and 5 is an opportunity also discussed at national level together with the strengthening of post-secondary education, which will provide qualifications linked to growing economic sectors.

In 2015, only 4.0% of enterprises offered **Initial Vocational Training (IVT)**, by economic activity, their choice of IVT varied according to their specificity but also their financial and material resources available.

CERONAV has been designated as the national training body for the further training of seafarers serving on board seagoing ships in order to achieve the minimum level of training required by the provisions of the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW 1978). As a national body, CERONAV fulfils the obligations of the Romanian State under international conventions and agreements relating to the training and further training of maritime and inland waterway personnel to which Romania is a party.

Academic

Education and research activities are set according to the Bologna Declaration, therefore each cycle of studies ensures that graduates obtain specific skills and competences, measurable and acknowledged by the certificate issued at the completion of the studies. Below you can find a table with the universities that have the most specific educational programs for the Blue Economy education programs. All the universities include bachelor, master and doctoral education.

Adult learning

The overall aim of the Romanian Institute for Adult Education – IREA is to improve the quality of adult education, and to identify ways to increase their participation in learning, and also to strengthen lifelong learning, both at individual and institutional levels. The main research directions within IREA are: development of key and basic skills, adult basic education, workplace learning and key competencies of adults, professionalisation of adult educators, the impact of new media on adult learning, intergenerational learning and active ageing, developing the concept of different support services offered to adults – e.g. counselling in adult education, delivery of innovative teaching and learning in the workplace, social inclusion and active citizenship through education.

The Romanian state ensure and sustain (including financially) access to education and continuing professional training for:

- Young people and adults who have not completed compulsory education;
- Young people who left the educational system before obtaining a professional qualification;
- People with special educational needs;
- Young people and adults who return to the country after a period of working abroad;
- Young people and adults who are residents in economically and socially disadvantaged communities;
- Employed people over 40 years old with a low educational background with low qualification levels;
- Students with a high risk of school failure;
- Any citizen who wants to benefit from permanent education.

Lifelong learning education is financed from public and private funds through public or private partnerships, with financing and co-financing from employers, non-governmental organisations.³

For example, Constanta Maritime University and CERONAV provides study programs on all levels of university and post university training, in order to train specialists for maritime transport activities and related activities.

3

bit.ly/3q0rNTn

II. SECTORS

Romania's coastline is 256 km long, representing 0,19% of the total coastline of EU-22 coastal Member States. The country's coastal zone (within a range of 10 km from the coast) covers 2.323 km, which amounts to 0,56% of the corresponding EU-22 Member States coastal area. Population and related social condition for maritime areas. Approximately 968.082 inhabitants live in the country's coastal regions, representing 4,53% of the country's total population. The coastal region employs approximately 1,1 million people, amounting to a share of 12,45% of the total employment in Romania and 0,54% of the labour force employed in all EU-22 coastal Member States.⁴

Romanian seaports recorded a traffic of 67.5 million tonnes in 2021, an absolute historical record. Compared to 2020, when the recorded traffic was 60.3 million tonnes, the increase is 11.77%. In 2021, the port of Constanta consolidated its position as a European hub for grain, recording an absolute record in grain traffic of 25.17 million tonnes, up from 21.9 million tonnes in 2020. Moreover, grain represents the largest share of total cargo traffic, with 37.3%. Other major cargo groups transiting the port of Constanta are: crude oil 10%, miscellaneous articles 9.2%, petroleum products 8.1%, iron ore, iron scrap 7.1%, fertilizers (natural and chemical) 6.1%, and solid mineral fuels with 5.1%.⁵

For the Romanian coastal area, **tourism** is a source of income and jobs. Besides the Black Sea as the main tourist attraction, its coastal area offers a natural potential that includes:

- nautical routes, nature sanctuaries (e.g. Danube Delta) and unique natural landscapes,
- health and treatment resources, including sources of natural mineral waters or healing shores, etc.
- cultural attractions, e.g. historical and architectural sites, film and music festivals,
- water sports in the Black Sea coastal area such as diving tourism can stimulate ecosystem understanding and preservation, as well as underwater archaeological heritage promotion.

4 Blue Career Centre of Eastern Mediterranean and Black Sea Market analysis for marine economic activities in Romania

5 bit.ly/3wN6xUV

- Fisheries heritage, traditions and ship-building attract travellers looking for experience-tourism and social dimensions.
- gastronomy and the unique flavours of the culinary heritage of a maritime region rich in multicultural influences

This sector includes occupations such as travel agent, boat operator, sales agent, water sports instructor and hotel and catering professions. Students who choose to attend Vocational Upper Secondary education can opt for specific specialisations in economics, gastronomy and tourism and receive a qualification diploma. National Association of Travel Agencies provides vocational training courses that graduates are able to manage independently, efficiently and professionally the main activities in the job description of a travel agent.

In the field of **Aquaculture** and **Marine Biotechnology**, Romania has a potential for educational development through the research infrastructure provided by:

- The University "Dunărea de Jos" Galați
- Three institutions specialised in inland water research: the Institute for Research, Development and Ecology Aquaculture, Fisheries and Aquaculture - Galați, the National Institute for Research and Development "Danube Delta" - Tulcea and the Research and Development Station for Fish Farming Nucet - Dâmbovița,
- One marine research institute: the National Institute for Marine Research and Development "Grigore Antipa" - Constanța.

The Research Station for Aquaculture and Aquatic Ecology Ezăreni of the University "Al.I.Cuza" Iasi, and a forestry research institute also addresses the issue of aquatic ecosystems in mountain waters and salmonid farming: Institute of Forest Research and Management – Bucharest. The University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine in Iasi, Bucharest, Cluj and Timisoara are also conducting research in the field of aquaculture.

Offshore Oil and Gas is a major conventional energy resource in the Romanian economy and one of the most important in the coastal area. Offshore oil and gas represents 50% of the oil and gas production in Romania. Romania holds a strategic geopolitical location in terms of access to markets and routes, including through the Black Sea, where Constanta Harbour is the largest and deepest port. Offshore oil and gas benefits from

innovation by private investors who are exploring and exploiting the marine reserves. Many people who want to pursue a career in this field attend a vocational college such as the University of Oil and Gas in Ploiesti, Constanta Maritime University. Graduates of these universities work in prestigious oil and gas companies in the country and abroad. They can work in various on-shore and off-shore locations, as well as in research institutions, research institutes, research centres, and education or higher education institutions, the latter requiring a Master's degree and doctoral degrees.

In the **Shipbuilding and Maintenance**: For the sector there are the following qualifications in the dual education system: Electrician Electrical and Energy Appliances and Equipment, Electrician Constructor, Electrician Low Voltage Operation, Energy Installation Measurement, Electromechanic Industrial Machinery and Installations, Electronics Technician for Apparatus and Equipment Metal Construction and Technological Equipment Locksmith, Shipbuilding Locksmith. Constanta Naval Shipyard is ranked among the largest newbuildings, ship repairs and conversions yards in Europe, the world's first-class shipbuilder for medium range products & chemical tankers. In Romanian academic education, maritime and oil universities offer a wide range of specialisations for those wishing to perfect their skills in this field.

Romania has a great potential for the **Fishing** sector. Romania's fisheries patrimony represents about 3% of the country's total area, comprising of 400.000 ha natural lakes (including the Danube Delta) and storage lakes; 95.682 ha growing farms; 6.673 ha nurseries; 66.000 km of rivers (of which 18.200 km in the mountain area and 1.075 km Danube river); 25.000 km² marine waters from the Exclusive Economic Zone of the Black Sea.⁶ Development Association for Social Assistance and Vocational Training, Centre for Vocational Training and Regional Development among other private companies are offering qualified courses for inland and coastal fishermen.

The **Maritime Transport** is provided by the direct access to the Black Sea through the three maritime ports: Constanta, Mangalia and Midia (the Port of Constanta being the main Romanian port, among the first ten European ports). The inland waterway transport, focused on the Danube river (1075 km along Romania), is provided through 29 inland waterway ports, the largest being the

ports of Galati, Braila and Tulcea, located on the maritime section of the Danube.⁷ Companies offering training in this field are partners with the Ministry of Transport, Port of Constanta, Federation of Romanian Transport Operators (FORT) and Union of Romanian Inland Ports (UPIR). HISTRIA SHIPMANAGEMENT SRL, together with the ownership companies collaborate with the support of the Constanta Shipyard, local training centres and certification authorities for new training and retraining programs for ratings, deck and engine. Cruise tourism is very important for local economic activity, as evidenced by the massive investments that have been made and what will follow, including the increase of the passenger terminal in Constanta, the establishment and modernization of the marinas along the Black Sea coast, as well as the traditional ports along the Danube from the Iron Gates to the Black Sea. In recent years, the number of foreign tourists arriving on Romanian territory choosing shipping has registered an increase of over 10% annually. The Romanian Naval Authority offers ship captain certification after training courses. With these certificates, depending on the type of vessel, you can then work in maritime tourism or cargo transport.

III. PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The **Ministry of National Education** is responsible for developing and implementing national policies and strategies for education and training, including those on VET. The Ministry designs and implements legislation in cooperation with the parties' stakeholders (academia, trade unions, teachers' associations, pupils/students, parents, public administration, companies and NGOs). It also approves funding and tuition plans, monitors, evaluates and controls, directly or through the competent bodies, the education system and the functioning of education providers, and coordinates the work of school inspectors.

The **National Centre for the Development of Vocational and Technical Education** is subordinated to the Ministry of National Education.

The main responsibilities of the centre's main responsibilities in initial vocational education and training are as follows:

⁶ Blue Career Centre of Eastern Mediterranean and Black Sea Market analysis for marine economic activities in Romania

- a) evaluating and proposing changes in policies and strategies, and coordinating their implementation;
- b) coordinating the development, implementation and revision of the national curriculum for vocational and technical education, evaluation and certification of the initial vocational education and training;
- c) supervising the development of the Vocational Training Standards for qualifications validated by the sectoral commissions (coordinated by the National Authority for Qualifications) and approved by the Ministry of Education;
- (d) ensuring the development and functioning of partnerships with stakeholders at national, regional, local level;
- (e) developing methodologies for quality assurance and monitoring training programs;
- (f) implementing continuous training programs for teachers/trainers.

The Institute of Education Sciences is a national research institution, development, innovation and training in education and youth. It contributes actively to innovation in education through expertise, training, education and research. Its mission is to provide scientific support for the latest approaches in education for authentic, motivated, active, innovative and creative learning. The Institute aims to play a key role in curriculum

development and teaching resources, as well as providing relevant on-the-job training, personalised and flexible for stakeholders in the education system.

Ministry of Labour and Social Justice develops and promotes policies within the continuing vocational training (adult vocational training), including for training for the unemployed, on-the-job apprenticeships, actions for NEETs (young people who are not in employment and do not follow any educational or training program vocational training) and traineeships for school leavers higher education.

The National Employment Agency coordinates training of jobseekers and NEETs at national level; it is carried out by the County Employment Agencies through their vocational training centres, regional centres for training centres, regional adult vocational training centres and other authorised public and private vocational training providers.

The Ministry of Transport of Romania is the national public authority in Romania which establishes the national policy in the field of transportation, the strategy and the specific regulations for the harmonisation and development of transport activities in the framework of the general policy of the Romanian Government.

The Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests promotes a unitary, coherent environmental policy. The water management represents the main infrastructure of the economical and social activities that influence the social-economical development of the country.

Port of Constanta - The ports of Constanta (with Constanta zone and Midia zone) and Mangalia and also the Tomis Marina are public-private maritime ports owned by the Romanian State which is responsible for their regulation and function. The National Company "Maritime Ports Administration" S.A. Constanta (MPA) is a company under the authority of the Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure. Within the Port of Constanta the maritime and cargo related services are mainly carried out by private companies in a competitive environment, applying the free market principles.

ANR - The Romanian Naval Authority is the state authority in the field of safety of navigation, the specialised technical body of the Romanian Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure

The Romanian Naval Force is part of the Romanian Army and carries out operations mainly in the Black Sea and on the Danube River. They are also commonly referred to as the Romanian Navy.

ACPART - National Authority for Qualifications in Higher Education;

ARACIS - Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education;

CNDIPT - National Centre for the Development of Vocational and Technical Education at Undergraduate level;

ANAT - National Association of Travel Agencies

INCDT - National Institute for Research and Development in Tourism

ANTREC - National Association of Rural Ecological and Cultural Tourism in Romania

Federation of Tourism Employers in Romania

IV. PLACEMENT AND RECRUITMENT AGENCIES

Two main strands of guidance and counselling are recognized and can be identified as such: one based in the education system (university and pre-university levels) and another one embedded into the administrative structures of the labour market (basically the public employment services but also services offered by other providers including continuing vocational training providers).

The national education law stipulates for:

- Counselling in primary education provided by teachers in cooperation with parents and school psychologists,
- Guidance and counselling in lower and upper secondary education provided mainly by pedagogical assistance offices, organised in schools with more than 800 pupils, subordinated to the county pedagogical assistance offices (schools with fewer than 800 pupils may receive counselling from the pedagogical assistance offices of larger schools).

In the higher education system, guidance and counselling is provided by career guidance and counselling centres of the universities with the main aim to facilitate the socio-professional transition of graduates from education to the labour market.

Guidance and counselling have also been included amongst the activities of the teaching staff with assessment criteria attached.

The National Agency for Employment (ANOFM) is a public institution of national interest in Romania, with legal personality, under the authority of the Ministry of Labour and Social Justice.

Stargate Crewing is an ISO certified, MLC compliant crew manning agency based in Constanta, Romania, a premier centre for maritime education on the Black Sea coast. They provide talented crew and repair teams for all types of sea-going vessels, drawing their recruits from some of the best trained seafarers and technicians in the business today.

Oil & Gas Recruitment handles requirements for temporary, permanent and contract placements mainly for the offshore, oil and gas industry and is the only Romanian Crewing Agency 100 % specialized in the offshore manpower supply, both locally and internationally.

Grup Servicii Petroliere has engineered a Human Resources comprehensive strategy to support the desire to join the offshore industry workforce by becoming a driller. In order to become one tough offshore industry specialist, one must be prepared for a new learning experience, as working offshore equals working in a highly demanding technological environment.

Nedcon Maritime as the largest independent Romanian manpower supply company for clients all over the world is offering numerous possibilities for those willing to get a well paid job in international locations for major maritime players.

Those who want a career in any sector of the Blue Economy can access the following websites:

- www.ainostri.ro
- www.romcrew.com
- www.crewingagencies.ro
- www.marinarionline.ro/

National Programs

The Educational and Vocational Guidance Department within the Institute of Educational Sciences developed the following projects:

- Euroguidance (1999-present): aims to promote the European dimension in guidance and counselling and provide information on mobility;
- Education for social-professional insertion of pupils. Compendium of methods and techniques used in career counselling: aims to identify the relevant methods for career guidance;
- GIRC-Guidance Innovation Relay Centres;
- Counsellor training program in pre-university education;
- Analysis of lifelong counselling needs: study on initial training programs counsellors (university, master, postgraduate) in Romania and EU;
- Monitoring system of graduates in the perspective of lifelong counselling: aims to identify the influence of counselling on career decision-making and on perceptions of graduates in relation to lifelong learning and also to shape a monitoring system of graduates from the perspective of lifelong counselling and guidance;
- GIANT-Guidance Innovative Actions and New Tools;
- NCP-VET-CO: aims to develop an effective network between the National Coordination Points in the participating countries and compiling a methodological guide for linking VET qualifications with the European Qualification Framework;
- Virtual Guidance: aims to increase ICT usage among counsellors providing guidance, and the training and skill development necessary for the provision of such services.⁸

8 Catalin Ghinararu (coordinator), Davidescu Adriana, Matei Monica, Romania VET in Europe – Country Report 2013

V. PROMOTIONAL VISITS

Aiming at attracting young people to the blue industry, the centre for career guidance of the **Association TEAM4Excellence** organize seminars, promotional visits and take part in professional fair events held at local, regional, as well as at national level. trainingclub.eu/bluegeneration/.

In the framework of the BlueGeneration project, the young people from VET schools (15-19 years old) and from youth organizations (16+) become aware about specific training for different job profiles in blue economy. VET learners and university students in the age group from 16-29, met mentors and started to build their blue professional career path.

To increase the awareness about working opportunities and to encourage mentorship in the Blue Economy, the Association collaborate with local NGOs:

The **Blue Career Centre** is set up within the framework of the MENTOR project - Blue Career Centre of Eastern Mediterranean and Black Sea, co-funded by the Brussels Executive Agency for SMEs (EASME) and implemented by seven partners from four countries in the Eastern Mediterranean and Black Sea region. The aim of the centre is to attract young people to careers in the blue economy by raising awareness of employment opportunities in the shipping and related sectors: cruise tourism, maritime aquaculture, offshore. cmu-edu.eu/bcc/

Women's International Shipping and Trading Association (WISTA) is an international networking organisation whose mission is to attract and support women, at the management level, in the maritime, trading and logistics sectors. The Romanian branch of WISTA is actively promoting the blue careers in schools and universities, as well as organizing events to support professional development of female in the maritime industry. wistainternational.com/association/wista-romania/

The **Romanian Shipmasters Association** is a non-governmental, non-profit, apolitical and independent organisation founded in 2018 with the purpose of representing the interests of Romanian shipmasters in Romania and abroad. The objective of the Association is to improve the situation of Romanian commanders and their social and professional integration. www.acnr.ro/

 Country Report **Spain**

I. TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES

Spain offers many different training opportunities related to the Blue Economy at either VET Training Centres, Universities, Employment Agencies or Sea Schools.

a. School system - VET Training - Formación profesional

School education in Spain is mandatory until the age of 16 at which stage students graduate with the qualification of E.S.O (Educación Secundaria Obligatoria – Mandatory Secondary School Education).

From the age of fifteen, students can choose to change to the Vocational Education and Training (VET) system. Vocational Education and Training offers more than 150 training course options within 26 professional sectors, with theoretical and practical study suitable for the various professional fields and students can achieve these certificates at various levels, obtaining the titles of ‘Auxiliary Technician’, ‘Technician’ or ‘Higher Technician’ in their professional field.

At the same time, for those who are unemployed or have left school early, the Spanish employment system provides opportunities to acquire VET certificates: Most of the VET modules (one or various subjects) corresponds to a Professional Certificate which can be acquired separately at

VET schools or employment agencies. The national employment system as well as NGOs and social services offer courses for these Professional VET Certificates for unemployed persons. Generally, the courses are run by public and private VET centres. Another pathway of acquiring professional VET certificates is through the validation of work experience and corresponding exams that are announced twice a year.

The standard VET education is scheduled over 2 years, with a total amount of 2.000 hours, 1.600 theoretical hours and 400 practical hours in a company. Some trainings include the possibility to do ‘Dual Training’ which means that the student receives more training and working within a company and signs a contract for a low wage.

The Vocational Education and Training System in Spain is organised by the following levels:

b. Basic Vocational Training Degrees

These degrees are for students that did not finish the mandatory secondary school (ESO) between the ages of 15 and 17 years, and they provide basic training for specific professions.

A completed Basic Vocational Training Degree corresponds to the level of the mandatory high school qualification (ESO). For the maritime professional sector there are 2 degrees:

- Basic Professional Degree in Maritime-Fishing Activities
- Basic Professional Degree in Recreational and Sports Boat Maintenance

c. Middle Grade Vocational Training Degrees

These degrees provide the title of technician for a specific subject. The training can be entered after finishing ESO, a Basic Vocational Training, or an access test. For the maritime professional sector there are 6 degrees offered in Spain:

- Aquaculture Technician
- Technician in Maintenance and Control of Ship and Boat Machinery
- Coastal Navigation and Fishing Technician
- Technician in Underwater and High-Pressure Operations
- Recreational Boat Maintenance Technician
- Technician in Maintenance of Wooden Structures and Furniture of Pleasure Boats

d. Higher Grade Vocational Training Degrees

These degrees can be accessed through a Middle Grade Degree, a High School Degree (Bachillerato), or an access test. They lead to the title of higher technician and allow the access to universities.

There are 3 degrees for the maritime professional sector:

- Higher Technician in Aquaculture
- Higher Technician in Ship and Boat Machinery Maintenance Organization
- Higher Technician in Maritime Transport and Deep-Sea Fishing

Several other professional sectors trained in high schools and VET centers, also offer possibilities to work in the maritime sector, e.g., 'Mechanical manufacturing', 'Energy and Water', 'Electricity and Electronics', 'Wood, Furniture and Cork', 'Food Industries', 'Installation and Maintenance', 'Hospitality and Tourism' and others. The full list of high schools and centers that offer VET training can be found at the official webpage from the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training, which also offers the option to filter the results for specific professional families, e.g., Maritime and

Fisheries². It also contains all the information for the validation of professional experience.

The 'integrated' VET centers, are specialized in specific Professional families. These specialized centers for Maritime and Fisheries offer all the major 2-year maritime VET studies as well as professional qualifications and titles, recognized by the General Directorate of the Merchant Navy.

1. CIFP Marítimo Zaporito (Cádiz)

Aquaculture, Ship and Boat Machinery, Maritime Transport, Fisheries

2. CIFP del Mar (Gijón)

Maritime transport, fisheries, Ship Machinery, professional certificates and official titles

3. CIFP Náuticosquera (Palma de Mallorca)

Maritime transport, fisheries, Ship machinery, professional certificates, and official titles

4. CIFP Centro de la Mar (Mahón)

Basic VET and technician in Maintenance of recreational boats. Professional certificates and official titles.

5. CIFP Hespérides (Cartagena)

Maritime transport, fisheries, Underwater operations (dual training), professional titles and qualifications

e. University studies

There are many studies that can be applied to work in the Blue Economy. These are various engineering studies that can be used in almost any sector, more so in Shipbuilding, Maritime Transport or Ocean Energy. Some examples of Bachelor's Degrees are:

- Civil Engineering
- Industrial Engineering
- Energy Engineering
- Nautical Engineering and Maritime Transport (has various names depending on the University, enable to be Merchant Navy Captain)
- Naval and Maritime Engineering (has various names depending on the University, enables to be Chief Engineer)

1 todofp.es/inicio.html

2 bit.ly/2JpNDII

Many other studies can be used to work in the Blue Economy, such as:

- Oceanography and Maritime Science
- Environmental Science / Biology / Biotechnology / Marine Biology
- Economics / International Trade and related
- Law and Consulting related

A large array of Master’s Degrees allow a specialization in a certain maritime-related field, e.g.:

- Master in Wind Power Engineering
- Shipbuilding and Marine Structures
- Aquaculture / Marine Science /Biotechnology
- Maritime Spatial Planning / GIS / Oceanography

Additionally, various military and public naval schools offer training to work in navy-related and maritime rescue positions, such as Centro Jovellanos in Madrid, from the Maritime Safety and Rescue Society or the Naval Military School in Marín.

Some important universities related to the studies mentioned above, offer the following Bachelor’s Degrees, Master and Doctorate Programs:

f. Specific titles

The sub-sectors of Maritime Transport and Fisheries require specific professional titles, corresponding to Deck positions (Captain, First Officer, etc.), Engineering (chief engineer, second engineer, etc.) and Interior (services like steward(esses) or cooks). Some of these professional titles are also required for large yachts (>24 m).

The basic requirement to work on any commercial vessel (>24 m) is the Basic Safety and Security Training (STCW95/10). Different positions on board, vessel sizes and vessel activities also require certain amounts of experience (months on a boat) and specific additional licenses and/ or qualifications (Ro-Ro, GDMSS...). These professional certificates are offered at private Sea Schools, specialized marine VET Centers, marine universities and marine professional training centers, and sometimes by national or regional employment agencies.

For work on pleasure vessels under 24 metres an array of different recreational titles is offered, which permit different commercial uses depending on the size of the vessel, the number of passengers and the distance from the coast. The highest title is the

1. Polytechnic University of Barcelona (Nautical Faculty)	Technical University focused on Engineering and Maritime Transport, but also Marine Sciences
2. Higher Technical School of Nautical and Naval Machinery (University of the Basque Country)	Renewable Energies, Naval Engineering, Shipbuilding, Maritime Transport and other sectors
3. Higher Technical School of Naval, Machines and Naval Radio electronics of Santa Cruz de Tenerife (University of La Laguna)	Technology and Marine Engineering, Maritime Transport
4. Santander Higher Technical Naval School (University of Cantabria)	Maritime and Marine Engineering, Maritime Transport
5. Higher Technical Naval and Machines School (University of A Coruña)	Maritime transport, Fisheries, Underwater operations (dual training), professional titles and qualifications
6. Higher School of Civil Navy (University of Oviedo)	Maritime Technologies, Maritime Transport, Marine Engineering
7. School of Marine, Nautical and Radio electronic Engineering (University of Cádiz)	Maritime Transport, Engineering, Radio Electronics, Marine Sciences
8. Faculty of Marine Sciences of (University of Las Palmas)	Marine Sciences, Oceanography, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Coastal Management
9. Higher Technical School of Naval and Oceanic Engineering (Polytechnic University of Cartagena)	Engineering, Shipbuilding
10. Higher Technical school of Naval and Oceanic Engineering (Polytechnic University of Madrid)	Engineering, Shipbuilding

Yacht Captain (“Capitán de Yate”), which allows the holder to take up to 6 paying passengers on board and which can be commercially endorsed to allow an increase of number of passengers to up to 12. All recreational titles are offered at private Sea Schools.

II. SECTORS

The Spanish Blue Economy employs over 757,500 people and generates around €26.3 billion in GVA. It is dominated by the coastal tourism sector, which contributed 75% to Blue Economy jobs and 67% to GVA in 2017. The living resources sector, fisheries and aquaculture, is also an important contributor, with 15% of jobs and 13% of GVA.

Coastal tourism is the most important sector in the Blue Economy in Spain, including a large variety of services and industries. The hospitality sector (including hotels and catering) and the nautical tourism industry are the two most important subsectors.

Hotels and Accommodation services are organized in umbrella associations at national level, e.g., the Spanish Confederation of Hotels and Tourist Accommodations (CEHAT) and at regional level, including the Grouping of Hotel Chains in the Balearic Islands or the Hotel Association of Barcelona (GHB). For **Catering** there are multiple associations, that represent bars, restaurants and pubs, at national level, like the Spanish Confederation of Catering Businesses (CEHE) or at regional level, e.g., the Association of Catering Enterprises of Madrid (AMER) or the Balearic Association of bars, restaurants and coffee shops (Restauración Mallorca).

Nautical Tourism includes recreational boating, cruises, marinas, water sports as well as maritime history tourism, recreational fishing, marine wildlife tourism and many other land-based related activities such as nautical museums and resorts. Closely related to this sector is the sector of repair and maintenance of recreational boats, which represents an important fraction of the jobs and value created. It is organized in National Organisations, such as the National Association of Nautical Companies (ANEN), the Spanish Association of Large Yachts (AEGY), the Spanish Maritime Cluster (CME), the Spanish Federation of Associations of Nautical Sports and Tourist Ports (FEAPDT) or the Spanish Confederation of Associations of Nautical Clubs (CEACNA) or the Spanish Alliance for Sustainable Recreational Fishery (APERS). There are smaller clusters for the

different regions, for example the Association of Nautical Companies of the Balearic Islands (AENIB).

Aquaculture and **Fisheries** are two important sectors in the Spanish Blue Economy. They organize themselves in different national and regional associations: for fisheries, the Spanish Fisheries Confederation (CEPESCA) or National Federation of Fishermen’s Guilds (FNCP) at national level; and many different associations at regional level or depending on what and where they fish, such as the Spanish Association for Cod Fishing Boats (AGARBA) or the Fisheries Cooperative for the Port of Vigo (ARVI).

The **Aquaculture** sector has different organizations at national and regional level. The most important organization at national level is the Spanish Aquaculture Business Association (APROMAR), others include the National Association of Continental Aquaculture (ESACUA) or the Spanish Aquaculture Society (SEA); there are also different regional associations and associations for the different species, such as National Association for Red Tuna Aquaculture (ANATUN) or the Galician Aquaculture Cluster (CETGA).

Another important sector in the Blue Economy in Spain is the **Shipbuilding** sector and here specifically shipyards and maritime equipment manufacturers. Also important are the industries that produce components for the use in other sectors, such as ocean energy, fisheries or aquaculture. These industries often group under national and regional clusters. At national level PYMAR is the association that brings together the main private shipyards in the country, being the managing body of the shipbuilding, repair and conversion sector. At regional level there exist other clusters, such as Aedimar (Cluster of the Galician Naval Sector), the Basque Maritime Forum, the Association of Maritime Industries of the Basque Country (ADIMDE), or the Maritime Technology Platform. The largest shipbuilding company in Spain is Navantia, with over 5.500 employees. An important part of the shipbuilding is related to recreational boats regarding maintenance, repair and construction of these vessels. Some important Spanish brands of recreational vessels are Rodman, De Antonio or Astondoa.

Maritime Transport represents a significant subsector and the most important ports in Spain are Algeciras, Valencia, Barcelona, Las Palmas and Bilbao. The maritime transport sector is grouped together under large umbrella organizations, such as the Association of Spanish Shipping Companies (ANAVE) or the Spanish Association

of Ship Consignees (ASECOB). Shipping agents often organize themselves in smaller umbrella organizations for the different ports, for example Barcelona, Algeciras or Bilbao. The Spanish Port System includes 46 ports of general interest, managed by 28 Port Authorities, whose coordination and efficiency is controlled by the government agency of Puertos del Estado, a body answerable to the Ministry of Transport, Mobility and the Urban Agenda that is responsible for implementing the government's port policy.

The pharmaceutical and **Biotechnology** sector in Spain clusters in National Organizations, such as the Spanish Association of Bio-companies (ASEBIO) or the Spanish Society of Biotechnology (SEBiot); and regional associations, for example CataloniaBio, BioIB (Balearic Islands), Madrid Biocluster or BioVal (Valencia).

The Offshore Wind Energy and **Ocean Energy** sector in Spain is not very developed, due to the sea-bed levels being too deep around Spain's coast. New technologies such as floating windfarms may produce an important development for the sector. Nevertheless, onshore wind power in Spain is an important industry, and there are many companies and shipyards producing parts, components and vessels for offshore wind farms in Europe. They are included in the associations for shipbuilding and maritime equipment manufacturers.

III. PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The established sectors such as coastal tourism, fisheries and aquaculture, maritime transport and shipbuilding have national and regional administrative departments.

The Coastal Tourism sector is represented by the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism, and under this Ministry, the Secretary of State for Tourism, has created the brand Turespaña, responsible for marketing Spain as a travel destination in the world. The different autonomous communities promote their regions through their councils for tourism.

The other part of coastal tourism, related to marinas, leisure boating, water sports, etc. depends on various administrations. The docks and the leisure boat marinas are located in the coastal public domain, being subject to the competence of all the administrations: the state administration due to its location on the coast, the autonomous administration because nautical sports are a transferred competence to the autonomous

regions, and the local administration, which determines the port uses and maintain different powers in relation to marinas.

The Maritime Transport, the general management of maritime navigation and the Spanish civil fleet are under the responsibility of the Ministry of Transport, Mobility and the Urban Agenda. The General Directorate of the Merchant Navy regulates and controls maritime traffic; the dispatch, registration and flagging of civilian ships as well as the ordering and execution of the technical, structural and equipment inspections and controls of civilian ships. They also regulate the professional titles for the Merchant Navy, recreational titles, the exams for these titles, as well as environmental issues according to international law (MARPOL).

The powers of execution of the government's port policy are exercised through the public body of State Ports, called Port Authorities, which provide general services as well as the management of the port's public domains.

The Maritime Safety and Rescue Society (SASEMAR) provides public services for the rescue of human life at sea, and for the prevention and fight against pollution of the marine environment, as well as monitoring and assistance services for maritime traffic, from maritime and navigation safety, towing and assistance to ships.

For Fisheries and Aquaculture, the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food is the administrative body. It controls Marine Protected Areas (MPA), the register of the fishing fleet, sport and recreational fishing, official fishing titles and exams and handles control, monitoring, inspection and licenses.

The administration responsible for the Ocean Energy sector is the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism, as well as the Secretariat of Energy and the General Directorate for Energy Policy and Mining, depending on the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge. Other relevant public bodies depending on this ministry are the General Directorate of the Coast and the Sea, and the Institute for the Diversification and Saving of Energy or the Spanish Office for Climate Change.

The Shipbuilding sector and manufacturing of marine equipment is the responsibility of the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism and the military shipbuilding and manufacturing is part of the Engineering and Naval Constructions Directorate at the Ministry of Defence.

The Spanish Chamber of Commerce coordinates the network of regional Chambers of Commerce

in Spain and acts as its representative at national and international governing bodies, as well as providing advisory services to companies and the Spanish government. Its mission is to promote and defend the general interests of trade, industry and services. The regional chambers include the blue economy as a specific sector they represent.

Other institutions that act as a link between enterprises and governing bodies are; PYMAR (the managing body of the shipbuilding, repair and conversion sector), and the Spanish Confederation of Enterprises (CEOE), both at national level; the Balearic Confederation of Enterprises (CAEB) or the Confederation of Enterprises of Madrid (CEIM) are some examples of confederations of enterprises that are present in the regions.

IV. PLACEMENT AGENCIES

The National Public Employment Service (SEPE) is an autonomous body attached to the Ministry of Labour, Migration and Social Security. SEPE, together with the Public Employment Services of the Autonomous Communities, form the National Employment System.

The activity they carry out is focused on workers, both unemployed and active, entrepreneurs

who have a business idea, young people and companies. It is carried out by the 52 provincial directorates, e.g., SOIB for the Balearic Islands, SOC for Catalonia or SAE for Andalucía, among others.

They manage employment itineraries for Young People through the Youth Guarantee Program, manage unemployment subsidies, help with the job search, and offer courses for unemployed and employed people, leading to professional certifications and career improvement.

At local level, many town halls have their own placement agencies, through their so called 'Local Development Agencies', that organize courses for unemployed people, employment programs and mentoring for disadvantaged youth. Some examples are PalmaActiva for the city of Palma de Mallorca, Barcelona Activa or 'Agencia para el Empleo' in Madrid.

The Youth Institute for Spain (INJUVE), manages the resources for young people at national and regional level, supporting NGOs and youth organizations.

There are many NGOs that work with young and disadvantaged people, mainly funded through the Youth Guarantee Program or the European Social Fund (ESF).

The largest NGOs that offer employment programs are the Red Cross and Caritas, supporting young and disadvantaged people through various programs, offering mentoring and helping young job seekers at national and regional level.

A large array of NGOs³ and Foundations work with disadvantaged youth at national and regional level, examples of other larger organisations working nation-wide are 'Fundación Adsis', 'Fundación Pere Tarrés', 'Fundación Federico Ozanam', 'Fundación Diagrama', 'Ecos do Sur', 'Cesal'.

The national and regional Chambers of Commerce also offer youth employment programs and courses through the Youth Guarantee Program.

Many saving banks in Spain have their own social Foundations⁴ that support social projects with over 1.000 million € per year and reaching vulnerable people; some examples are youth and employment programs and supporting vulnerable communities. The largest banks with foundations in Spain are 'CaixaBank', BBVA and Banco Santander.

V. PROMOTIONAL VISITS

To promote employment in the Blue Economy to youth under 30 and especially NEETs requires a differentiated look at the target group, considering their age, educational standard, social background and needs.

Typical groups of young people in Spain, depending on the studies, age and employment are:

- young people that are finishing mandatory secondary school (15-16 years old) and high school (17-18 years old). These youth are found in public and private high schools. They require more general information about the Blue Economy and its sub-sectors and are mostly interested in further training opportunities (Middle Grade and Higher-Grade Vocational Training, University Studies).
- High schools and specific VET training centres are visited by students of Middle Grade Vocational Training Degrees (16-18 years old) and Higher Vocational Training students (18+ years old) that are more interested in career opportunities, mentoring and job placement for their specific field of study, e.g. VET students of Tourism might want information about cruise ships or VET students of mechanical

engineering are interested in Leisure Boat Maintenance.

- Youth at Adult Education Centres (18+ years old) are more interested in mentoring and job opportunities with a low academic profile.
- Students at Universities in the age group from 18-29, are interested in career opportunities, mentoring and job placement in their specific field of study. They are also interested in internships and job opportunities abroad.
- Young, disadvantaged people can be found at various NGOs, and are more interested in job offers with a low academic profile, short training options and dual VET.
- In Employment Agencies, young unemployed people are more interested in mentoring, specific training for different job profiles and job opportunities.

Contact details for educational services can be found at:

- 1 The State Registry of Non-University Teaching Centers (RCD)⁵ lists all high schools, VET Training centers, Adult Education Centres, and professional qualifications, and all the non-university training centres for the different provinces. Every autonomous region has its own lists.
- 2 The QEDU Service⁶ from the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities lists all University Studies in the different regions of Spain.
- 3 Employment agencies: SEPE⁷ is the national employment agency in Spain with many other employment services organised at regional or local level through different town halls.
- 4 Every region in Spain has its own regional Chamber of Commerce, which also can be found through the central Chamber of Commerce⁸.
- 5 NGOs should be researched at local level. The Spanish Youth Institute (INJUVE)⁹ is currently compiling a list of all the resources for youth employment at national level.

3 www.fundacionlealtad.org/ong/?name_filter=size

4 www.ceca.es/Flip_ObraSocial2017/index.html#78

5 www.educacion.gob.es/centros/selectaut.do

6 bit.ly/3pXJYcm

7 www.sepe.es/HomeSepe

8 www.camara.es/

9 www.injuve.es/

BlueGeneration Project

An Ocean of
Opportunities

THE PROJECT IS IMPLEMENTED BY

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The Blue Generation project is funded by Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway through the EEA and Norway Grants for Youth Employment